

Deliverable 1.1

Specification of the data sets' quality and utility label

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DELIVERABLE SUMMARY	
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QUANTUM summary	QUANTUM aims at developing and implementing a label mechanism that could be ideally adopted in the future HealthData@EU. QUANTUM builds on 5 technical work packages (WPs). WP1 conceptualises and provides technical specifications for a data quality, utility, and maturity label. WP2 designs and tests, at small-scale, the label. WP3 implements the labelling mechanism in a number of data holders. WP4 engages the data quality users' community; and, WP5 outreaches other interested parties, including other initiatives building HealthData@EU.
Deliverable abstract	This deliverable aims at providing technical specification of the data sets' quality and utility label (task 1.3) based on previous work on DQ&U dimension conceptualization (task 1.1) and related consensus process (task 1.2). The joint output of tasks 1.1., 1.2 and 1.3 have conformed to the deliverable 1.1 (D1.1) that operationalizes the consensus into technical specifications that will allow to define and design the data quality and utility label per se. The technical specifications displayed in this deliverable focus on the metrics, values/weights and format of the data quality and utility label and respective indicators (e.g., score, categories, binary/"stamp" format).
Keywords	data quality label, data quality dimension, nominal group, measurement, thresholds, quality level

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10	HEALTH-RI	STICHTING HEALTH-RI	NL
11	EUHA	EUROPEAN UNIVERSITY HOSPITAL ALLIANCE	BE
12	AP-HP	ASSISTANCE PUBLIQUE HÔPITAUX DE PARIS	FR
13	VIB	VLAAMS INSTITUUT VOOR BIOTECHNOLOGIE	BE
14	CIPH	HRVATSKI ZAVOD ZA JAVNO ZDRAVSTVO	HR
15	HUS	HUS-YHTYMA	FI
16	THL	TERVEYDEN JA HYVINVOINNIN LAITOS	FI
17	ECRIN	ECRIN EUROPEAN CLINICAL RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE NETWORK	FR
18	BFARM	BUNDESINSTITUT FÜR ARZNEIMITTEL UND MEDIZINPRODUKTE	DE
19	HIQA	HEALTH INFORMATION AND QUALITY AUTHORITY	IE
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22	e-helse	DIREKTORAT FOR E-HELSE	NO
23	U.PORTO	UNIVERSIDADE DO PORTO	PT
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QUANTUM
THE HEALTH DATA QUALITY LABEL

Developing a data quality and utility label for the European Health Data Space.

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

CHU	Centre hospitalier universitaire
CSIC	Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas
D	Deliverable
DQ&U	Data Quality & Utility
DQV	Data Quality Vocabulary
EHDS	European Health Data Space
EU	European Union
FHI	Folkehelseinstituttet
HDAB	Health Data Access Body
Health	Application Profile
DCAT-AP	
PROV-O	Provenance Ontology
TEHDAS	Towards a European Health Data Space
UK	United Kingdom
UKDS	United Kingdom Data Service
WP	Work Package

Preface

Quantum approach: concepts

This deliverable, “Specification of a dataset quality and utility label”, focuses on two aspects: **quality and fit-for-use**. Neither maturity nor fit-for-purpose are addressed. However, maturity is discussed within the scope of Deliverable 1.2 (D.1.2).

In the QUANTUM approach:

Quality refers to features that describe the content of a dataset, typically completeness, uniqueness, accuracy, validity, timeliness, and consistency of the data.

Fit-for-use is equivalent to a dataset's "potential" utility, typically information that describes the dataset in a standard manner, such as source, provenance or lineage, content, distribution, etc. Fit-for-use talks about the "potential" utility of a dataset, while the actual utility can only be informed by the user experience—in QUANTUM, the actual utility is referred to as fit-for-purpose.

Fit-for-purpose refers to the actual utility of an accessed dataset according to the objective of the health data request. The information necessary to evaluate fit-for-purpose depends on the user's experience. This information needs to be added to the description of a dataset as a fit-for-purpose meta-data.

Maturity is a feature at the data holder level. It refers to the level of automation of data and data quality management procedures.

Underlying principles leading to the QUANTUM Quality and Utility Label Specification

QUANTUM's approach to developing a quality and utility label builds on several principles:

- The label specification has to provide data users with **meaningful information about the dataset's quality and fit-for-use**. This implies providing information that is granular enough to meet users' needs when discovering datasets of potential interest.
- The label **has to be agnostic to purpose**. This implies recognising that purposedness is case-specific, and only the final data user can inform on the actual value of a specific dataset for specific use.
- The label **has to be agnostic to the type of data**. This property aims to meet the need for a single and inclusive label mechanism. This decision entails renouncing to include some specificities of non-tabular data.
- The label specification **has to cover the provisions of Article 78** in Chapter IV of the European Health Data Space Regulation. This deliverable has focused on letters a (data documentation), b (technical quality) and d (coverage) in paragraph 3, which are specific for quality and fit-for-use. Please note that letters c (data quality management), e (access and provision), and f (data enrichment) are addressed in the deliverable on data holders' maturity, where a maturity matrix is being developed in deliverable 1.2.
- The label specification is **independent of the level of maturity of the data holders** who have to implement it. This implies the need to be inclusive and engage any potential data holder. Please note that the maturity matrix in deliverable 1.2 shows the pathway for data holders to progress towards automation.

Introduction

The Deliverable D1.1 “Specification of the data sets’ quality and utility label”, resulting from the activities of tasks 1.1, 1.2 & 1.3, provides the conceptualization of the DQ&U (Data Quality and Utility) label. It is based on desk research and expert consultations (carried out in task 1.1) and on a formal consensus process following Delphi methodology (conducted in task 1.2), followed by the selection and refinement of a relevant and consensual set of criteria (conducted in task 1.3) for assessing the quality and usefulness of datasets.

The aim of this document is to operationalize the outcome of the previous tasks in order to define specifications focused on evaluating the quality of a dataset. In this way, data holders will be able to assess and provide information that can be translated into a numerical label.

The dataset labelling mechanism in QUANTUM is meant to respond to the requirements provided in the HealthData@EU legislation (see article 78 [here](#)). It will form part of the metadata describing HealthData@EU datasets when they are catalogued, and will be interoperable with existing metadata documentation standards and future health dataset catalogues.

Finally, the label specification will contain elements addressing fit-for-use (potential utility), technical quality and data holders’ maturity. The specification will be tested and piloted with QUANTUM stakeholders (small scale in WP2 and mid-scale in WP3). Ultimately, the label specification will be integrated as part of the HealthData@EU datasets’ cataloguing procedures. In this report we address the specification for fit-for-use (potential utility) and technical quality.

This report is structured as follows:

- [Chapter 1](#) first provides an overview of the main outputs of tasks 1.1 & 1.2 on which the final specifications identified in this report are based.
- [Chapter 2](#) is dedicated to the selected consensus methodology of task 1.3 to prioritise and operationalize the outcomes of tasks 1.1 & 1.2.
- [Chapter 3](#) describes how the label specifications were identified, comprising:
 - The process of refining the dimensions retained from the Delphi survey;
 - The process of defining corresponding operational measure(s) and values for the remaining dimensions;
 - Information on the two online surveys that were conducted about the relevance of the proposed measures & values, the weighting of quality dimensions & measures, and the definition of dataset quality levels.
- [The conclusion](#) provides a summary of the main findings including an outlook on how the presented results will feed the upcoming work packages.

1. Main outcomes of task 1.1 and task 1.2

Task 1.1 focused on an extensive and systematic literature review along with individual expert consultations. Existing data quality frameworks were identified to avoid overlaps and to provide consistent and reliable definitions for each dimension within their respective categories. This process produced a set of 54 data quality (DQ) dimensions (major axes of the label) and categories (subdimensions), which were the input for Task 1.2.

1.1. Theoretical basis (Task 1.1)

Starting from the requirements laid down in the then draft version of the EHDS Regulation, task 1.1 of the QUANTUM project explored the state of the art and built the theoretical basis for the further tasks to achieve consensus and operationalise definitions for a data quality and utility label. This included researching existing initiatives as well as standards and literature, consulting with experts from different groups having to work with a future quality and utility label, and consolidating the material into definitions for a set of data quality and utility dimensions.

Article 78.3 of the Regulation on the European Health Data Space¹ states that “*The data quality and utility label shall cover the following elements, where applicable*”. These elements are grouped in six topics ([see Table 1](#)), which will subsequently be called “EHDS category” for clear distinction from categories of data quality, a term frequently used in literature.

Table 1 - EHDS categories and elements

EHDS category	EHDS element
data documentation	meta-data
	support documentation
	data dictionary
	format and standards used
	provenance
	data model
technical quality	completeness
	uniqueness
	accuracy
	validity
	timeliness
	consistency
data quality management processes (level of maturity)	review
	audit processes

¹ Regulation on the European Health Data Space, final text, 2025-01-08: <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/PE-76-2024-INIT/en/pdf>

	biases examination
coverage	time period
	population coverage
	representation of multi-disciplinary electronic health data ²
	representativity of population sampled
	average timeframe in which a natural person appears in a dataset
access and provision	time between the collection of the electronic health data and their addition to the dataset
	time to provide electronic health data following electronic health data access application approval
data modifications	merging and adding data to an existing dataset
	including links with other datasets

The EHDS category “data quality management processes” is listed here for completeness but has not been processed in task 1.1 as this belongs to the data holder maturity model covered by task 1.4.

1.1.1. Wording

In the following, some concepts need to be addressed consistently.

The DQV³ provides some crucial definitions:

- **Category** represents a group of quality dimensions in which a common type of information is used as a quality indicator. Categories are meant to systematically organise dimensions. The Data Quality Vocabulary defines no specific cardinality constraints for `dqv:inCategory`, since distinct quality frameworks might have different perspectives over a dimension. A dimension may therefore be associated with more than one category. However, those who define new quality metrics should try to avoid this as much as possible and assign only one category to the dimensions they define.
- **Dimension** represents criteria relevant for assessing quality. Each quality dimension must have one or more metrics to measure it. A Quality Dimension is a quality-related characteristic of a dataset relevant to the user (e.g., validity).
- **Metric** represents a standard to measure a quality dimension. A Quality Metric gives a procedure for measuring a data quality dimension, which is abstract, by observing a concrete quality indicator. There are usually multiple metrics per dimension.

² The element “representation of multi-disciplinary electronic health data” was contained in the legislative proposal as of May 2022 but not in the final text. Task 1.1 was already quite advanced when this change was published, therefore the element was not removed from the working material and left to the consensus process to assess its relevance.

³ Data Quality Vocabulary, 2016 <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dqv/>

- *Measurement* represents the evaluation of a given dataset (or dataset distribution) against a specific quality metric. An observation (instance of dqv:QualityMeasurement) assigns a value in a given unit to a Metric.

1.1.2. Sources

In the following steps it was crucial to consider how the results of QUANTUM will finally fit together with standards like HealthDCAT-AP, DQV, PROV-O etc.

Given the extensive experience and knowledge within the QUANTUM consortium, several other sources (quality frameworks, literature, as well as related projects like TEHDAS1) were already known to be relevant. Additionally, PubMed and Google Scholar were searched with keywords “data quality” and “data utility” in combination with “framework”, “label”, “dimensions”, “metrics”, “criteria”, “indicators”, “model”, “analysis”, “measurement” and “assessment”.

Findings in citations, literature reviews, meta-analyses etc. were traced back to the original publication. Publications were scrutinised for relevance considering the scope, presence of clearly described and ideally explicitly defined quality and / or utility dimensions and applicability to the range of data in EHDS secondary use. Literature in German was kept for further examination, if any value additional to the sources in English seemed possible.

354 definitions or criteria were extracted from these sources, forming the raw material for further processing.

1.1.3. Processing the material

Different ways to hierarchically organise definitions were harmonised into categories and dimensions with sub-dimensions, the latter not being defined in DQV. The differentiation between dimensions and sub-dimensions was not very precise, though.

In discussions with partners from WP1 and coordination it was decided to assign the hierarchy level “dimension” to all of them. The resulting variety in the level of granularity of definitions was not regarded a weakness but rather a chance for the following consensus process to choose the best balance between the conflicting goals of definitions being generic enough for the range of EHDS’ categories of electronic data for secondary use and being specific enough to be measurable and provide a helpful information. Also, it was important to identify definitions that were actually *metrics*, providing a rule for measuring a more abstract concept (*dimension*).

After assuring consistent spelling and harmonising the used terms duplicates were removed, leaving **280 definitions**.

Several related or overlapping concepts are named quite inconsistently throughout literature, sometimes even swapped, therefore concepts had to be clarified and the most commonly used term assigned to it.

Also, literature reveals a group of concepts (namely *consistency*, *validity*, *coherence*, *conformance*, *concordance*, *plausibility* and *comparability*) which all are about comparing 'things' (in the

broadest sense) to each other or some other given knowledge or rule. They can be distinguished by looking at the kind of comparison predominantly described in literature:

- *Consistency* comprises all kinds of comparisons (one thing against another version of itself, several related things against each other or against constraints, ...) and can be paraphrased with “free from contradiction”, with the special case of temporal consistency looking at one thing at different points in time.
- *Validity* compares one thing (usually a variable, data field or data value) against a format, relational definition, value domain etc.
- *Coherence* is very similar, but predominantly compares several related things (variables, data fields or data values) against a format, relational definition, value domain etc., therefore also addressing consistency throughout the dataset.
- For *conformance* we could not make a clear distinction from validity as described above. In its definitions "conforming to some specification, format etc." usually has the meaning of "being valid (validated, validatable) against some specification, format etc".
- *Plausibility* shows a range of relatively vague definitions, but can be summarised as a stronger version of consistency, in that it requires consistency (contradictions are never plausible) and adds the soft rule to be “in agreement” with expectations (raised by some other knowledge like related variables, 'real-world knowledge', literature,). Especially temporal plausibility is often mixed with temporal consistency.
- *Concordance* is a more general and weak version of consistency and plausibility, often described by “agreement on comparability”.
- *Comparability*, focusing on comparing the same things across datasets, can be regarded as an 'external version' of coherence which focuses on the analysability of a single dataset (therefore 'internal'). Also coherence includes the 'compatibility' of different but related things with each other (e.g. precision of start date and end date).

The next step inspected the scope of definitions. Those out of scope were removed, if rephrasing to the scope of QUANTUM was not possible (e.g. if they did not represent quality or utility, or if they described the quality of something else than a dataset).

Other definitions were in scope but extremely broad (e.g. by listing several quite different aspects in one dimension). If their definitions allowed splitting into more specific dimensions they were kept as a reserve to fill gaps later.

Opposed to this, other definitions had to be removed for being too specific (e.g. only applicable in certain situations like a specific data type, and not being rephrasable in a more general way). Surprisingly many definitions were removed because of quite vague wording, often avoiding a real definition by only referring to synonyms. This might be caused by the same challenge of finding definitions as universally applicable as possible, while any added degree of specificity reduces this range. Sometimes concepts (such as those related ones described above) were not well distinguished.

The remaining alternative definitions for each dimension were inspected conjointly to select the 'good ones' (in terms of being close to the predominant interpretation, being precise, being comprehensible while staying concise), and in some cases to add a version combining the most aptly worded aspects from the given alternatives.

The language of all remaining definitions was harmonised without changing the meaning, e.g.

by rearranging to start with the phrase “[dimension] refers to...”, where applicable.

1.1.4. Consulting with experts

In this project, project-internal expert consultation played a pivotal role in incorporating practical aspects of data quality and utility and ensuring the robustness and relevance of our work. Conceptual hierarchies, the clarity of definitions and existing data quality frameworks or standards were discussed in many meetings as well as in written input from partners and contributors.

An interview with the author of the freshly published paper “Frameworks, Dimensions, Definitions of Aspects, and Assessment Methods for the Appraisal of Quality of Health Data for Secondary Use: Comprehensive Overview of Reviews”⁴ added a lot of depth to this understanding. One learning of this was that not only the different data types or secondary use purposes, but also the many and often complex steps in the data life cycle make an overall assessment of data quality and utility more challenging.

QUANTUM tasks 2.1 and 1.1 developed a survey to data holders to gather information on data scopes and uses, as well as current data quality practices, resulting in 22 responses from QUANTUM partners and 5 responses external to the project. The complete survey results are detailed in Annex III of Milestone 2.1. Aspects relevant for this chapter were context information about the data, including how it's used and its types, as well as currently used data quality methodologies and standards. This information was examined to detect any potential gaps in the research performed at this stage. The fact that no additional quality framework or other source referenced new definitions improved confidence in the exhaustiveness and relevance of the previous results.

A poll was sent to project partners representing data users, data holders, data analysts and data quality managers, to clarify remaining ambiguities or to give preferences in 23 dimensions. A total of 20 responses were collected, very clearly confirming the intermediate results in the majority of cases. 6 definitions were revised and slightly rephrased due to only relative majorities (e.g. 9:6 votes for the two best alternatives).

1.1.5. Synthesis

After synthesis of the abovementioned a set of **54 distinct quality and utility dimensions** remained, along with their definitions, sources (marked as modified, if applicable) and comments.

Dimensions were then matched to the related EHDS element as listed above. Several dimensions could match the same EHDS element, e.g. because different concepts fell under

⁴ Declerck et al., 2024 - Frameworks, Dimensions, Definitions of Aspects, and Assessment Methods for the Appraisal of Quality of Health Data for Secondary Use: Comprehensive Overview of Reviews# <https://medinform.jmir.org/2024/1/e51560/PDF>

one umbrella term, or because different levels of granularity remained for the consensus process. 15 of the dimensions from literature and expert consultations did not align with any EHDS element. For these a grouping was proposed into the additional elements *plausibility*, *coherence* and *comparability* (all three in the EHDS category *technical quality*) as well as the element *access* in the EHDS category *access and provision*. This grouping of dimensions is given for convenience of further steps but can be changed at will, if some other grouping seems practical.

These results -including the shown list of EHDS categories and elements, a small glossary of additional terms extracted from literature, and the list of 45 sources providing definitions or being mentioned somewhere else in the process- were fed into subsequent tasks, especially the directly following consensus process.

Thus, the main output of Task 1.1 resulted in a list of 54 quality dimensions (to be found in [Annex 1](#)), organised into five EHDS categories and 24 EHDS elements. This consolidated list formed the conceptual map that served as the substrate for the Delphi study, which aimed to achieve consensus on the relevance and priority of these dimensions using the RAND/UCLA method.

1.2. Consensus process for a data quality and utility label -Task 1.2)

Task 1.2 builds upon the results from Task 1.1 translating the most determinant and representative dimensions for the health domain, into a Delphi process. The goal is to achieve consensus on the most relevant and priority dimensions for evaluating the quality and utility of datasets, thereby aiding in the development of a data quality, utility, and maturity labelling tool.

The consensus process methodology carried out through the Delphi is detailed in the Milestone report M1.2 that can be found in [Annex 2](#).

In total, two Delphi rounds were carried out. The process allowed for a quantitative and qualitative (via comment section) rating.

The main outputs will be displayed below and were extracted from the Milestone report M1.2. These results are central to understand the specifications on the data sets' quality and utility label developed in the following task 1.3. For the detailed analysis of the Delphi and the methodology linked to the result's analysis (statistical tests, bias prevention, analysis of anchoring effects, distribution of the respondents etc.), please refer to Milestone report M1.2 in Annex 2.

1.2.1. First round

The initial round of the Delphi consultation was centred on evaluating **the relevance** of the presented dimensions. The participants were presented with the following question while evaluating each DQ dimension: *"If you were to decide on the quality and utility of a dataset. How RELEVANT would you consider the following dimensions, on a scale from 1 (Not relevant at all) to 9 (Absolutely relevant)?"*. The first round achieved a satisfactory level of participation, with 109 participants adequately representing all the different roles involved in the European Health Data Space (44 data holders (40%); 41 data users (38%) and 24 HDAB (22%)). The total number of experts contacted was 648 (participation rate 17%).

Out of the identified 54 dimensions in task 1.1, 34 dimensions ([Table 1](#)) reached the level of agreement (Interpercentile Range Adjusted for Symmetry (IPRAS) > Interpercentile Range(IPR)) and obtained a median score in the top segment (7-9) while 20 DQ dimensions did not reach the necessary agreement level with an IPR greater than IPRAS ([Table 3](#)). The comment analysis performed on these 20 dimensions confirmed the lack of agreement and the overlap of some of these dimensions with the other 34 dimensions part of the accepted group.

1.2.2. Second round

After having identified 34 data quality dimensions as the most **relevant** in assessing the quality and utility of health data, the aim of the second round was to prioritise these dimensions by **weighting their priority** in terms of valuing the quality and utility of a dataset. This round had

an adequate level of participation with 66 out of 109 initial participants (a 39.44% drop-off) and adequately represented all the different roles involved in the EHDS. The outputs were analysed using the same methodology as the first round, comparing median scores and agreement levels based on IPR and IPRAS indices.

For dimensions that did not reach consensus on priority in this second round, the decision was made not to exclude them, given their relevance and the high agreement observed in the initial round. These dimensions were classified as '**recommended or optional**' for implementation in the QUANTUM label tool and will not influence the quality scoring or ranking criteria of the tool.

Additionally, as per the first round, a qualitative assessment of participant comments on dimensions lacking priority consensus was performed. Both researchers agreed that their findings were aligned with the decision to leave those categories as optional and out of the scope of the quality scoring or ranking criteria to be implemented as the QUANTUM label.

Out of the 34 retained dimensions from the first Delphi round, **26 dimensions** reached an adequate level of agreement considering them relevant and priority. While 8 dimensions had an IPR greater than their IPRAS with also the lowest mean, therefore not reaching the desired level. These 8 dimensions are highlighted in the table below ([see Table 2](#)) and are the ones that were considered "recommended or optional".

Table 2 - 34 DQ Dimensions from Delphi 2nd Round

DQ_Dimension	Median	Mean	Std_Dev	Lower_P	Upper_P	IPR	IPRAS	IQR	Min	Max	Segment	Decision
Metadata granularity	8	7.55	1.63	7	9	2	2.15	2	1	9	7-9	Accepted
Data dictionary granularity	8	7.39	1.66	7	9	2	2.15	2	2	9	7-9	Accepted
Compliance	8	7.29	1.67	7	8	1	1.4	2.75	1	9	7-9	Accepted
Data origin provenance	7	7.20	1.61	7	8	1	1.4	1.75	3	9	7-9	Accepted
Data derivation provenance	7	6.86	1.79	6	8	2	0.65	2	1	9	7-9	('IPRAS<IPR, median:', 7.0)
Traceability	7	6.74	1.83	6	8	2	0.65	2	2	9	7-9	('IPRAS<IPR, median:', 7.0)
Trustworthiness	8	7.38	1.84	7	9	2	2.15	2	2	9	7-9	Accepted
Data model granularity	7	7.09	1.69	6.5	8	1.5	1.025	2	2	9	7-9	('IPRAS<IPR, median:', 7.0)
Completeness	8	7.88	1.12	7.5	9	1.5	2.525	2	5	9	7-9	Accepted
Capture completeness	7	6.55	1.65	6	7	1	0.1	2.75	1	9	7-9	('IPRAS<IPR, median:', 7.0)
Data completeness	7.5	7.39	1.22	7	8	1	1.4	1	3	9	7-9	Accepted
Accuracy	8	7.85	1.32	8	9	1	2.9	2	3	9	7-9	Accepted
Precision	7	7.24	1.37	7	8	1	1.4	1	3	9	7-9	Accepted
Reliability	8	7.77	1.35	7.5	9	1.5	2.525	2	3	9	7-9	Accepted
Data falsification	7	6.86	2.07	6	8	2	0.65	3	1	9	7-9	('IPRAS<IPR, median:', 7.0)
Validity	8	7.88	1.20	7	9	2	2.15	2	4	9	7-9	Accepted
Syntactic validity	8	7.44	1.51	7	8	1	1.4	1.75	1	9	7-9	Accepted
Relational validity	8	7.23	1.61	7	8	1	1.4	2	1	9	7-9	Accepted
Computational validity	7	6.94	1.71	6.5	8	1.5	1.025	2	1	9	7-9	('IPRAS<IPR, median:', 7.0)
Consistency	8	7.89	1.16	7	9	2	2.15	2	5	9	7-9	Accepted
Relational consistency	8	7.39	1.58	7	8	1	1.4	2	2	9	7-9	Accepted
Coherence	8	7.67	1.40	7	9	2	2.15	2	3	9	7-9	Accepted
Internal coherence	8	7.27	1.64	7	8	1	1.4	1	2	9	7-9	Accepted
Format coherence	7	7.03	1.64	7	8	1	1.4	2	2	9	7-9	Accepted
Semantic coherence	8	7.53	1.65	7	9	2	2.15	2	2	9	7-9	Accepted
Comparability	7	7.38	1.51	7	8	1	1.4	2	2	9	7-9	Accepted
Temporal comparability	7	7.09	1.72	7	8	1	1.4	2	2	9	7-9	Accepted
Temporal coverage	7	6.98	1.42	6	8	2	0.65	2	4	9	7-9	('IPRAS<IPR, median:', 7.0)
Population coverage	8	7.17	1.77	7	8	1	1.4	1.75	1	9	7-9	Accepted
Population representativity	8	7.77	1.33	7	9	2	2.15	2	3	9	7-9	Accepted
Availability	8	7.45	1.70	7	9	2	2.15	2	1	9	7-9	Accepted
Accessibility	8	7.68	1.44	7	9	2	2.15	2	3	9	7-9	Accepted
Use permissiveness	7.5	7.17	1.89	7	8	1	1.4	2	1	9	7-9	Accepted
Data linkage documentation	7	7.03	1.75	6.5	8	1.5	1.025	2.75	3	9	7-9	('IPRAS<IPR, median:', 7.0)

1.2.3. Link to task 1.3

The rigorous consensus methodology and comprehensive stakeholder engagement have allowed these identified 26 DQ dimensions with a high level of agreement on their relevance and prime role in assessing the quality and utility of a dataset providing a reliable foundation for building an efficient labelling tool and clear specification defined in the subsequent task 1.3. The following sections, representing the work done in task 1.3, will explain how consensus was reached first on the definition of each retained DQ dimensions, and then on their measurements and thresholds.

2. Nominal group methodology

With regards to the need of **defining commonly agreed measures, values and thresholds** for the label, based on the fine tuned dimensions conceptualised in Task 1.1 and agreed upon via the Delphi process in Task 1.2 (according to their relevance and priority level), the nominal group methodology was selected.

Its main objective was to **make decisions on the most relevant metrics** of quality and utility dimensions to build the QUANTUM label specifications.

Defining a label requires a common understanding of what quality and utility means; particularly, when the challenge is to provide a concept that is agnostic to types of data and purposes.

Attention point

The methodological choice to stay **agnostic to data type and usage** was defined at the very beginning of the project. This implies that activities linked to “definition of data types & main usage families” are outside the scope of this deliverable. Quality dimensions should be intrinsic features and not depend on data type. This also represents a prerequisite for the label to be applied to a variety of stakeholders dealing with different types of data and maturity levels. In this context, it was also defined that a **fit-for-purpose approach** should be discarded within QUANTUM Work Package 1 as the conceptualization and operationalization of the label should not depend on a particular user’s experience or some particular dataset.

2.1. Nominal group preparation

The nominal group is a qualitative methodology meant to reach consensus on complex topics in a short period of time. The subjects are usually experts relevant to the topic of interest. The nominal group has one conductor leading the discussions, rapporteurs taking notes and observers to report back to the conductor about the dynamics of the discussions. Neither rapporteurs nor observers were allowed to take part in the discussions.

For this purpose, 16 organisations ([see Table 3](#)) were selected by the QUANTUM coordinator, allowing a balanced representation of the main roles in the EHDS (Health Data Access Bodies (HDABs), data holders & data users) - and of the countries represented in the QUANTUM project.

In order to ensure high relevance of the discussions, the selected organisations have then been asked to nominate outstanding experts in the field of data quality and utility.

Table 3 - List of selected experts by field, organisation and country representation

#	Field	Organisation	Country
1	HDAB	SPMS	Portugal
2	HDAB	FHI	Norway
3	HDAB	BfArM	Germany
4	HDAB	NIJZ	Slovenia
5	HDAB	Health-RI	Netherlands
6	Data Holder	ERASMUS MC	Netherlands
7	Data Holder	VIB	Belgium
8	Data Holder	AP-HP	France
9	Data Holder	CHU Bordeaux	France
10	Data Holder	HIQA	Ireland
11	Data Holder	HUS	Finland
12	Authorised participant	BBMRI - ERIC	EU
13	Data user	ECRIN	EU
14	Data user	CESSDA/UKDS	UK
15	Data user	UPV	Spain
16	Data user	University of Porto	Portugal

The nominal group took the form of a two-day face-to-face workshop in Brussels on July 4th and 5th. A concept note ([see Annex 3](#)) had been shared with the experts beforehand clarifying the scope of this activity and asking them to do some preparatory work (by reading the 26 dimensions selected from the Delphi process).

Indeed, the nominal group was **not meant** to cover the following aspects:

- **Fit-for-purpose:** QUANTUM understands fit-for-purpose, meeting predefined quality standards, as a consequence of the actual use of a particular dataset and has to reflect the user's experience for his/her particular purpose.
- **Data holders' maturity:** maturity represents the data holders' capacity to manage data and data quality. This is a property of the data holder, not of the datasets.

Instead, it was **to be dedicated to:**

- **Quality & Potential utility / Fit-for-use** (satisfying the needs of various users across different contexts and applications): defined by a number of dimensions agreed in the first round of the Delphi survey and prioritised in the second one.
- **Metrics:** experts were asked to get agreement on
 - What potential **measures** quantify each of the dimensions prioritised in the Delphi survey;
 - What **operational definitions** would be appropriate for those measures;
 - What **values** those measures should take;
 - What **thresholds** should be used to report on the quality and utility of a dataset.

2.2. Nominal group execution

The nominal group meeting was held on July 4th & 5th 2024 at the CSIC Brussels office and the following tasks were carried out:

- **Disambiguation of the list of dimensions from the Delphi process**

The moderator of the nominal group meeting went through the departing dimensions definitions one by one with the experts. With the results of the discussion displayed live, the experts were able to see how their statements were assimilated and had the opportunity to correct any misunderstandings.
- **Overarching definition of the dimension measures**

The experts' objective was to produce an operational definition for the measure(s) of each DQ&U dimension. A Klaxoon board (collaborative tool) was set up to enable experts to share their ideas, bearing in mind that there could be more than one measure per dimension, and to vote for ideas raised by other experts.

In the planning phase of the nominal group, it was suggested that the following sections could be addressed through online surveys, if necessary:

- Agreement on measures and values;
- Weighting of data dimensions;
- Weighting of measures by dimension (for dimensions with more than one measure);
- Evaluation of dataset quality levels.

This option was confirmed after the face-to-face meeting, given the in-depth nature of the discussions on disambiguation of the selected Delphi dimensions.

2.3. Nominal group follow-up

In the wake of the workshop, the Task 1.3 coordination team (composed of the QUANTUM project coordinator and task 1.3 leads & co-leads) worked together to consolidate the ideas of dimension measures put forward by the experts. To this end, the team refined the initial

definitions and deduced the respective value ranges, keeping in mind the feasibility of the end result.

2.3.1. Online survey for agreement on data dimension measures

To confirm the relevance to the QUANTUM label specifications of the measurement(s) and value ranges by dimension, a first online survey (using Google forms) was sent to the experts ([see Annex 4](#)) with the same process for each dimension's measure:

- A content proposal (definition, value range and recommended approach);
- Two questions:
 - a) *For dimension X, do you agree with measure Y to be used as part of the quality & fit-for-use labelling of a dataset in the context of HealthData@EU (answer on Likert scale 1 to 9)?*
 - b) *For measure Y, would you suggest a different approach (free text answer)?*

The survey was sent out on July 23rd, with a deadline extended to the end of August (due to the summer vacation period) and a total of 15 out of 16 experts responded.

Based on the experts' answers, the Task 1.3 coordination team conducted both a quantitative assessment (calculating medians from the Likert scale scores) and a qualitative review (considering all comments provided by the respondents).

2.3.2. Online survey on weighting data dimensions, measures and thresholds

An explanatory meeting was held on September 3rd with the experts, in the interests of accountability, to clarify the changes made to the measures after the first survey (confirming their accuracy) and to introduce the final task of the consensus group.

The second online survey (based on LimeSurvey) was sent out the same day ([see Annex 5](#)) with a deadline by September 13th. It consisted of three sections:

- Weighting of data dimensions;
- Weighting of measures per dimension (for dimensions with two measures);
- Evaluation of dataset quality levels (in the hypothesis of a 5-star rating system).

The email sent to the experts with the survey also included the final list of dimension measures with revised definitions & value ranges based on experts' votes & comments from the first survey.

To conclude the nominal group activity, the results (derived from 15 responses) were analysed by the Task 1.3 coordination team to confirm their relevance to the definition of label specifications.

3. Label specification based on nominal group results

3.1. DQ&U dimensions

During the nominal group workshop, an important part of the discussions focused on disambiguating the list of dimensions retained from the Delphi process.

The original table, with the 26 dimensions for which there was substantial agreement on their relevance and which were prioritised for label specification, can be found below ([see Table 4](#)). The changes made during the nominal group workshop are highlighted in the following way:

- Dimensions are ranked according to the agreement reached in terms of priority (highest at the top);
- The dimensions in green (12) / red (8) / blue (6) have been retained / deleted / slightly modified (or summarised within more general concepts), respectively, at the end of the workshop.

Table 4 - List of DQ&U dimensions (post-Delphi version)

Category	Dimension	Definition (as is)
Technical quality	Accuracy	Accuracy refers to the degree to which data correctly describes what it was designed to measure (the "real world" entity).
Technical quality	Completeness	Completeness refers to the degree to which all required information is present in a particular dataset.
Technical quality	Reliability	Reliability refers to how closely the data reflect what it was designed to measure and is this consistent over time.
Technical quality	Consistency	Consistency refers to the degree to which data has attributes that are free from contradiction and are coherent with other data in a specific context of use. It can be either or both among data regarding one entity and across similar data for comparable entities.
Technical quality	Validity	Validity refers to the degree to which representations of data in a dataset conform to internal or external formatting, relational, or computational definitions.
Coverage	Population representativity	Population representativity refers to the degree to which the data adequately represent the population in question.
Access and provision	Accessibility	Accessibility refers to the degree to which data is easily obtainable, clearly presented in a way that can be understood and available in a suitable format.
Technical quality	Coherence	Coherence refers to the degree to which aspects relevant for analysability are used consistently throughout a dataset or

Category	Dimension	Definition (as is)
		across different datasets or versions of one dataset. Examples: - Are formats the same (e.g., of different date variables)? - Is the precision of values the same (e.g., age always approximated to years)? - Are references to entities consistent so that information about the same entity is properly linked across parts of the dataset?
Data documentation	Metadata granularity	Metadata granularity refers to the availability, comprehensiveness and level of detail of metadata that help users understand the data being used.
Technical quality	Semantic coherence	Semantic coherence refers to the degree to which the same value means the same throughout a dataset or across different datasets or versions of one dataset, improving analysability.
Access and provision	Availability	Availability refers to the degree to which data is present, obtainable and ready for use.
Data documentation	Data dictionary granularity	Data dictionary granularity refers to the availability, comprehensiveness and level of detail of the data dictionary.
Data documentation	Trustworthiness	Trustworthiness refers to the degree to which context information fosters trust in the data, e.g. by documenting agents involved in the provenance of data, data validation routines, the provenance of available provenance information etc.
Technical quality	Syntactic validity	Syntactic validity refers to the degree to which data conforms to the syntax (e.g. format, type, range) of its definition.
Technical quality	Relational consistency	Relational consistency refers to the degree to which data has attributes that are free from relational contradiction, i.e. each entity shall be represented by at most one identifiable data unit, or by multiple but consistent identifiable units.
Data documentation	Compliance	Compliance refers to the degree to which data has attributes that adhere to standards, conventions or regulations in force and similar rules relating to data quality in a specific context of use.
Technical quality	Internal coherence	Internal coherence refers to the degree to which it is possible to combine and make use of related data within a dataset based on consistent use of aspects relevant for analysability, such as formats, standards and methods.
Technical quality	Relational validity	Relational validity refers to the degree to which a dataset conforms to the data model.
Coverage	Population coverage	Population coverage refers to the coverage rate of the population in question.
Technical quality	Data completeness	Data completeness refers to the degree of data attributes being present in a dataset without reference to specific data values.
Access and provision	Use permissiveness	Use permissiveness refers to the degree of permissiveness that licences and requirements for ethical and data governance

Category	Dimension	Definition (as is)
		approval grant to a user for the intended use.
Technical quality	Comparability	Comparability refers to how the consistent use of definitions, standards and methods facilitates comparison of data.
Technical quality	Precision	Precision refers to the degree of approximation by which data can represent reality (e.g. numerical resolution or the number of categories).
Data documentation	Data origin provenance	Data origin provenance means a description of the source of the original or raw data prior to any subsequent processing or transformation, including context, purpose, method and technology of data generation.
Technical quality	Temporal comparability	Temporal comparability refers to how the consistent use of definitions, standards and methods facilitates comparison of data over time.
Technical quality	Format coherence	Format coherence refers to the degree to which formats are used consistently throughout a dataset or across different datasets or versions of one dataset, improving analysability.

Table 4: dimensions in green (12) / red (8) / blue (6) have been retained / deleted / slightly modified (or summarised within more general concepts), respectively.

Thus, of the 26 dimensions presented to the experts, **12 were validated** during the workshop, their definitions having been revised accordingly ([see Table 5](#)), while the corresponding operational measures remained to be found.

Table 5 - List of DQ&U dimensions (final version)

EHDS category	Dimension (by priority)	Dimension definition
Technical quality	Accuracy	Accuracy refers to the degree to which observations correctly describe what it was designed to measure
Technical quality	Precision	Precision refers to the degree of approximation by which data can represent reality
Technical quality	Coherence	Coherence is defined as the dimension that expresses how different parts of the dataset are uniform in their representation and meaning over time, such as formats, semantics (stability of the data models), and methods
Technical quality	Consistency	Consistency refers to the degree to which data has attributes that are plausible and are uniform with other data and over time
Data documentation	Metadata scope	Metadata scope refers to the availability, comprehensiveness, level of detail of metadata and data dictionary that help users understand the data being used
Technical quality	Validity	Validity refers to the degree to which representations of data in a dataset conform to the specification of a data model or data models
Access and provision	Accessibility	Accessibility refers to the dataset being accompanied by clear and transparent access and usage conditions
Data documentation	Compliance	Compliance refers to the degree to which data has attributes that adhere to ethical standards, conventions, protocols or regulations
Coverage	Population representativity	Population representativity refers to the degree to which the data adequately represent the population in question
Coverage	Population coverage	Population coverage refers to the degree to which a dataset includes the potential eligible population
Technical quality	Completeness	Completeness refers to the degree to which all information that could be available is present in a particular dataset
Data documentation	Data provenance	Data provenance means a description of the source of the data, including context, purpose, method and technology of data generation, documenting agents involved in the provenance of data, data validation routines, source data verification, traceability of changes, and quality control of data

3.2. Operational measures of DQ&U dimensions

Based on the ideas put forward by the experts at the workshop, the coordination team drew up a first draft of a correspondence table (see Table 6) between data dimensions, measurements and value ranges.

Table 6 - List of dimension measures & values (post-nominal group version)

Dimension	Measure #	Measure label	Value range
Accessibility	1	Availability of a data access & usage policy at the time of release of the dataset	0: No policy available 1: Basic policy available 2: Comprehensive policy available
	2	Number of publications per year using the dataset	Number per year
	3	Average time from data access application to data release for a specific dataset	0: More than 6 months 1: 3 to 6 months 2: 1 to 3 months 3: Less than 1 month
Population coverage	1	Coverage Rate (percentage of the eligible population represented in the dataset)	[0-1] (percentage) <80%: Limited coverage 80-90%: Good coverage 90-95%: Very good coverage 95-100%: Near-universal or universal coverage
Population representativity	1	How closely does the observed population match the expected population?	0: No information of method of collection 1: Non representative sample 2: Representative sample 3: Universe of data
Compliance	1	Is there an ethical approval number or a similar reference associated with this dataset?	0: No 1: No, but an explanation is given, why this is not applicable 2: Yes
	2	Is there documentation of compliance with ethical standards, conventions, protocols or regulations?	0: No. 1: Documentation of applicable ethical standards, conventions, protocols or regulations, but no documentation of deviations or compliance. 2: Documentation of applicable ethical standards, conventions, protocols or regulations, as well as documentation of deviations or compliance.

Dimension	Measure #	Measure label	Value range
Data provenance	1	Is the source of the dataset documented?	0: no data available 1: data is available
	2	Is traceability documented?	0: No documentation of provenance 1: Some documentation of provenance not complying with agent, activity and derivation standards 2: Full documentation of provenance complying with agent, activity and derivation standards
Metadata scope	1	Existence of comprehensive standardised metadata	0: Non-standardised metadata 1: Partially complying with standardised metadata model (e.g. HealthDCAT-AP) 2: Fully complying with standardised metadata model (e.g. HealthDCAT-AP)
	2	Existence of an exhaustive data dictionary at variable level	0: No data dictionary 1: Partial data dictionary: some variables described with basic information (i.e., names and brief definitions) 2: Complete data dictionary: all variables described with detailed information (i.e., names, definitions, units, allowed values, etc.)
Accuracy	1	Availability of an accuracy report	0: No such report 1: Information on the efforts to ensure accuracy 2: Statistical information on accuracy
Coherence	1	Availability of a coherence report	0: No such report 1: Partial information available 2: Complete information on changes over time
Completeness	1	Availability of a completeness report	0: No 1: Some variables are analysed for completeness 2: All variables are analysed for completeness
Consistency	1	Availability of a consistency report	0: No 1: Yes
Precision	1	Availability of a precision report	0: No 1: Yes
Validity	1	Availability of a conformance	0: No

Dimension	Measure #	Measure label	Value range
		report for the data model	1: Yes

The above table was used to develop **the first online survey assessing the experts' agreement on the data dimension measures (labels and value ranges)**.

The survey results were compiled to display the median relevance score (following likert scale 1 to 9) per measure ([see Table 7](#)).

Attention point

The methodological choice of using the median rather than the mean was based on the assumption that the median is less prone to outliers, particularly when the survey covers a small number of individuals.

Table 7 - Relevance of dimension measures (median scores)

Dimension	Measure #1	Measure #2	Measure #3
Accessibility	8.0	5.0	8.0
Population coverage	8.0		
Population representativity	8.0		
Compliance	8.0	8.0	
Data Provenance	8.0	8.0	
Metadata Scope	9.0	8.0	
Accuracy	7.0		
Coherence	8.0		
Completeness	8.0		
Consistency	7.0		
Precision	8.0		
Validity	8.0		

First, the Task 1.3 coordination team decided to consider only those measures with a relevance score greater than or equal to 7.

Then, all experts' comments were classified into six main categories (three for the measure definition and three for the value range) to facilitate their review:

- Suggesting different measure definition;
- No clear measure definition;
- Clear measure definition;
- Suggesting different definitions of the value range;
- No clear definition of the value range;
- Clear definition of the value range.

After examining the comments one by one, the following modifications were decided and the list of dimension measures & values finalised accordingly ([see Table 8](#)):

- Accessibility: Exclude Measure #2 (lack of agreement);
- Population representativity: Reformulate value range for Measure #1;
- Compliance: Exclude Measure #1 (too specific in comparison with Measure #2 and not including all the compliance aspects);
- Data provenance: Reformulate value range for Measure #1 and definition & value range for Measure #2;
- Accuracy, Coherence, Completeness, Consistency, Precision & Validity: Reformulate definition & value range for Measure #1 of each.

Table 8 - List of dimension measures & values (final version)

Dimension	Measure #	Measure label	Value range
Accessibility	1	Availability of a data access & usage policy at the time of release of the dataset	0: No policy available 1: Basic policy available 2: Comprehensive policy available
	2	Average time from data access application to data release for a specific dataset	0: More than 6 months 1: 3 to 6 months 2: 1 to 3 months 3: Less than 1 month
Population coverage	1	Coverage Rate (percentage of the eligible population represented in the dataset)	[0-1] (percentage) <80%: Limited coverage 80 - <90%: Good coverage 90 - <95%: Very good coverage 95 - 100%: Near-universal or universal coverage
Population representativity	1	How closely does the observed population represent the expected population?	0: No information on sampling methodology 1: Sampling information does not demonstrate the sample representativity 2: Sampling information demonstrates the sample representativity 3: Dataset contains all expected population
Compliance	1	Is there documentation of compliance with ethical standards, conventions, protocols or regulations?	0: No. 1: Documentation of applicable ethical standards, conventions, protocols or regulations, but no documentation of deviations or compliance. 2: Documentation of applicable ethical standards, conventions, protocols or regulations, as well as documentation of

Dimension	Measure #	Measure label	Value range
			deviations or compliance.
Data provenance	1	Is the source of the dataset documented?	0: No source is documented 1: Source is documented
	2	Are the processes and operations on the data documented?	0: No documentation on data processes and operations 1: Some documentation on data processes and operations but not complying with PROV-O standards 2: Full documentation on data processes and operations complying with PROV-O standards
Metadata scope	1	Existence of comprehensive standardised metadata	0: Non-standardised metadata 1: Partially complying with standardised metadata model (e.g. HealthDCAT-AP) 2: Fully complying with standardised metadata model (e.g. HealthDCAT-AP)
	2	Existence of an exhaustive data dictionary at variable level	0: No data dictionary 1: Partial data dictionary: some variables described with basic information (i.e., names and brief definitions) 2: Complete data dictionary: all variables described with detailed information (i.e., names, definitions, units, allowed values, etc.)
Accuracy	1	Is the accuracy of the dataset documented?	0: Accuracy not documented 1: Information on the efforts to ensure accuracy is provided (non statistical information provided) 2: Statistical information on accuracy is provided at variable and/or individual level
Coherence	1	Is coherence of the dataset documented?	0: Coherence not documented 1: Coherence documented for some entities, attributes and relations in the dataset 2: Coherence documented for all entities, attributes and relations in the dataset
Completeness	1	Is completeness of the dataset documented?	0: Completeness not documented 1: Some variables are analysed for completeness 2: All variables are analysed for completeness

Dimension	Measure #	Measure label	Value range
Consistency	1	Is the consistency of the dataset documented?	0: Consistency not documented 1: Consistency of some variables is documented 2: Consistency of all variables is documented
Precision	1	Is the precision of the dataset documented?	0: Precision not documented 1: Precision of some variables is documented 2: Precision of all variables is documented
Validity	1	Availability of a conformance report for the data model	0: No report available 1: Report available for validity of some variables 2: Report available for validity of all variables

Considering the final list of dimension measures & values, a **second online survey** was carried out to collect the final information required for QUANTUM label specifications, including:

- Weighting of the selected data dimensions;
- Weighting of the selected measures per dimension (for those with two measures);
- Evaluation of threshold values to define quality levels for datasets.

3.3. Weighting of data dimensions

In the first section of the survey, experts were asked to assess the relevance of the DQ&U dimensions in the QUANTUM label definition, by allocating 100 tokens between the available dimensions (with priority dimensions having more tokens).

The table below (see Table 9) shows the Median & Average weights per dimension.

In order to obtain a sum (Total) of 100, with integer weights for all dimensions, to facilitate the development and practical use of the labelling tool, a two-stage score revision was carried out, first (SR1) giving priority to the Average weight values, and second (SR2) modifying the weight of the Accuracy dimension (so the sum of dimension weights = 100).

For the QUANTUM tool development (in WP2), the values in the “SR2” column should be considered.

Table 9 - Weighting of data dimensions

Dimension	Median	Average	SR1	SR2
Accessibility	10	9,1	9	9
Accuracy	10	10,6	11	10
Coherence	9	9,8	10	10
Completeness	10	9,7	10	10
Compliance	7	7,7	8	8
Consistency	10	10,0	10	10
Data Provenance	9	7,9	8	8
Metadata Scope	9	7,9	8	8
Population coverage	6	6,2	6	6
Population representativity	8	6,9	7	7
Precision	6	6,2	6	6
Validity	8	8,1	8	8
Total	102	100,0	101	100

3.4. Weighting of measures per dimension

In the second part of the survey, participants were asked to assess the relevance of the dimensions' measures for the QUANTUM label, by allocating 100 tokens between the available measures per dimension (towards evaluating if they were equally important or, if not, the ratio of importance between them).

In view of the above (see [Table 8](#) as a reminder), only the dimensions "Accessibility", "Data provenance" and "Metadata scope" were concerned by this section.

The results (see [Table 10](#)) show no significant difference between the proposed measures for the "Accessibility" and "Data provenance" dimensions, while the presence of a data dictionary (at variable level) appears to be more critical than having standardised metadata available for the "Metadata scope" dimension.

For the QUANTUM tool development (in WP2), values in the "Median" column should be considered.

Table 10 - Weighting of measures per dimension

Dimension	Measure #	Measure label	Median	Average
Accessibility	1	Availability of a data access & usage policy at the time of release of the dataset	50	53,6
	2	Average time from data access application to data release for a specific dataset	50	46,4
Data provenance	1	Is the source of the dataset documented?	50	48,8
	2	Are the processes and operations on the data documented?	50	51,2
Metadata scope	1	Existence of comprehensive standardised metadata	40	41,0
	2	Existence of an exhaustive data dictionary at variable level	60	59,0

3.5. Defining quality levels for datasets

In the final part of the survey, participants were asked to propose threshold values for defining the quality levels of a dataset, indicating the percentages (using only integer values) required to obtain 1, 2, 3, 4 or 5 stars, as a draft mechanism for displaying the final score.

The results below (see [Table 11](#)) show the Minimum, Maximum, Range, Median & Average percentages by dataset quality level.

For the QUANTUM tool development (in WP2), values in the “Median” column should be considered (each quality level starting with the median integer value, e.g. a score of 44% means the dataset is rated 1 star).

Table 11 - Evaluation of dataset quality levels

Dataset quality level	Minimum	Maximum	Range	Median	Average
★	0	60	60	25	28,0
★★	20	66	46	45	44,8
★★★	40	72	32	60	60,2
★★★★	60	90	30	80	77,3
★★★★★	80	100	20	90	91,7

Points to consider when developing the QUANTUM tool, based on experts' feedback:

- It must be possible to rate a dataset with 0 stars (if it does not reach the score of 25%);
- Alternatives to the dataset quality assessment format (star or other) should be tested at a later stage, e.g. replacing stars with a gauge bar (more or less filled) , asking for feedback from data users;
- In addition, a ranking by dimension score could be included (so that a 3-star dataset could be chosen over a 4-star one, because the former has a higher value in terms of Metadata scope). Thus, datasets could potentially be listed in a global table with, next to each dataset, its overall evaluation and scores for all dimensions (with filters available for all fields displayed).

Conclusion

The joint output of QUANTUM tasks 1.1., 1.2 and 1.3 have conformed to the deliverable 1.1 (D1.1) that operationalizes existing health data quality dimensions into technical specifications thus providing a technical solution for the development of the Article 78 of the European Health Data Space Regulation. Thanks to the use of a robust and proven consensus-building methodology, with the continuous involvement of experts throughout the process, the results presented above can serve as a solid reference for the WP2 team in charge of developing the first version of the QUANTUM labelling tool.

Thus, from an initial list of 54 DQ&U dimensions issued from expert consultations and an extensive literature review carried out in task 1.1, the task 1.2 coordination team was able to reach an adequate level of agreement through the Delphi process on 26 DQ&U dimensions. Task 1.3 was then in charge to operationalize those outputs together with selected experts forming a nominal group. In sum, 12 key dimensions were retained within task 1.3 (detailing their definitions, measurements and associated value ranges).

In addition, a scoring matrix was developed to enable a dataset to be evaluated using specific criteria (dimensions and associated measures) and thus assigned an overall quality score.

It is important to remember that the overall objective of WP1, and more specifically D1.1, was to conceptualise a label designed for use by various stakeholders who engage with different types of data and maturity levels. In this context, it was also defined that a fit-for-purpose approach should be discarded within QUANTUM WP1 as the conceptualization and operationalization of the label should not depend on a particular user's experience or some particular dataset. Quality dimensions are hereby considered to be intrinsic features and not depend on data type.

Looking ahead and to ensure the final operability of this health data quality and utility label, the specification features should be iteratively refined and disseminated in alignment with the QUANTUM tool development and testing cycle (tasks 2.3, 2.4 and 3.2).

Annexes

Annex 1 - Task 1.1 Handover to Task 1.2

EHDS elements

Art. 56.3: "The data quality and utility label shall cover the following elements, where applicable:"		
EHDS category	EHDS element	comment
data documentation	meta-data	
data documentation	support documentation	
data documentation	data dictionary	
data documentation	format and standards used	
data documentation	provenance	
data documentation	data model	
technical quality	completeness	
technical quality	uniqueness	
technical quality	accuracy	
technical quality	validity	
technical quality	timeliness	
technical quality	consistency	
data quality management processes (level of maturity)	review	Not considered, because the maturity of the data quality management processes is out of scope of task T1.1, it will be addressed in T1.4, compare the GA: "D1.2 – Specification for the assessment of data holders' maturity" and "task 1.4 will develop a maturity model for data holders"
data quality management processes (level of maturity)	audit processes	
data quality management processes (level of maturity)	biases examination	

coverage	representation of multi-disciplinary electronic health data	
coverage	representativity of population sampled	
coverage	average timeframe in which a natural person appears in a dataset	
access and provision	time between the collection of the electronic health data and their addition to the dataset	
access and provision	time to provide electronic health data following electronic health data access application approval	
data modifications	merging and adding data to an existing dataset	
data modifications	including links with other dataset	

Dimensions for handover

This tab contains consolidated data quality dimensions, their definitions, their alignment with the EHDS regulation and additional comments.						
EHDS category	EHDS element	dimension	dimension_definition	source(s)	comment	change due to poll voting?
data documentation	meta-data	Metadata granularity	Metadata granularity refers to the availability, comprehensiveness and level of detail of metadata that help users understand the data being used.	modified Statistics Finland, 2022	More of a metric (but not specific enough to be measurable right away) is HDR UK Data Utility Framework (Gordon et al, 2021): "Proportion of metadata (as in the current metadata specification) which is available in the expected format."	Renaming of the "availability" dimensions to "granularity", which was not used consistently before, and it describes the concept more clearly, compare poll comment "The availability concept only addresses presence. To include level of detail, the definition should be in a higher level, e.g. "Data model completeness" (may include both the presence and the detail) ...", but 'completeness' is used as a dimension, so that might be confusing.

data documentation	support documentation	Support documentation granularity	Support documentation granularity refers to the availability, comprehensiveness and level of detail of data documentation, that complements other more formal and structured types of data documentation such as metadata, a data dictionary etc. Support documentation gives more context and guidelines for human users to understand and be able to work with the data.	modified HDR UK Data Utility Framework (Gordon et al, 2021)	ad metrics: Health Information and Quality Authority, 2018 proposes that it "can be assessed by establishing whether or not the necessary documentation is up to date and available to data users. This includes documentation to accompany preliminary and revised data."	see availability vs. granularity
data documentation	data dictionary	Data dictionary granularity	Data dictionary granularity refers to the availability, comprehensiveness and level of detail of the data dictionary.	modified Kahn et al., 2015		see availability vs. granularity
data documentation	format and standards used	Compliance	Compliance refers to the degree to which data has attributes that adhere to standards, conventions or regulations in force and similar rules relating to data quality in a specific context of use.	modified ISO/IEC 25012	This differs from validity, which compares used vs. documented formats, and from format coherence and comparability, which compare format 1 vs. format 2, but not format 1 vs. standard format.	
data documentation	format and standards used	Mapping completeness	Mapping completeness refers to the degree to which every entity or attribute in the domain of interest can be	modified ISO 8000-8:2015		

			represented by the formats and standards used.			
data documentation	provenance	Provenance granularity	Provenance granularity refers to the availability, comprehensiveness and level of detail of a provenance record that describes the people, institutions, entities, and activities involved in producing, influencing, or delivering a dataset.	PROV-DM, 2013	ad metrics: A few of the PROV elements that might be relevant for quality, utility and trustworthiness, which might therefore be considered in assessing 'granularity that matters', not just granularity for its own sake: prov:Agent, prov:wasGeneratedBy, prov:wasDerivedFrom, prov:Person, prov:Organization, prov:wasQuotedFrom, prov:Derivation, prov:PrimarySource, prov:qualifiedPrimarySource, prov:Generation PROV-AQ:has_provenance PROV-DC:Publisher	
data documentation	provenance	Data origin provenance	Data origin provenance means a description of the source of the original or raw data prior to any subsequent processing or transformation, including context, purpose, method and technology of data generation.	Kahn et al, Table 1. Data Quality Assessment Documentation and Reporting Recommendations, 2015. Aerts et al., 2021. PROV-DM, 2013		

data documentation	provenance	Data derivation provenance	Data derivation provenance means a description of how the target data was obtained from the source data, including any changes made to the data.	modified Kahn et al, Table 1. Data Quality Assessment Documentation and Reporting Recommendations, 2015	This may comprise data corrections, calculations, recoding, remapping etc, therefore also making visible any loss and degradation of information content.	
data documentation	provenance	Traceability	Traceability refers to the degree to which data can be traced back to its origin.	modified Statistics Finland, 2022	It combines data origin provenance and data derivation provenance.	
data documentation	provenance	Data agency provenance	Data agency provenance means a description of agents bearing responsibility for data and activities that happened. Agents can be persons (e.g. data stewards, scientists, health care personnel etc) and organisations, but also software agents and others.	PROV-DM, 2013. modified Kahn et al, Table 1. Data Quality Assessment Documentation and Reporting Recommendations, 2015	Strongly related to trustworthiness: Data published by a respected independent organization may be considered more trustworthy than that from a lobby organization; a claim by a well-known scientist with an established track record may be more believed than a claim by a new student; a calculation performed by an established software library may be more reliable than by a one-off program.	
data documentation	provenance	Trustworthiness	Trustworthiness refers to the degree to which context information fosters trust in the data, e.g. by documenting agents involved in the provenance of data, data validation routines, the provenance of available provenance information	PROV-DM, 2013. Sáez et al., 2012	This dimension seems very broad, but it might be an aggregate of several metrics measuring different aspects of provenance (see above), maybe also including plausibility.	

			etc.			
data documentation	data model	Data model granularity	Data model granularity refers to the availability, comprehensiveness and level of detail of the data model.	modified HDR UK Data Utility Framework (Gordon et al, 2021)		see availability vs. granularity
technical quality	completeness	Completeness	Completeness refers to the degree to which all required information is present in a particular dataset.	Zaveri et al., 2016		
technical quality	completeness	Capture completeness	Capture completeness refers to the degree to which potential cases have been recorded.	modified Declerck et al., 2024		
technical quality	completeness	Data completeness	Data completeness refers to the degree of data attributes being present in a dataset without reference to specific data values.	modified Kahn et al., 2016	ad metrics: different sources and patterns of missingness might be considered: missing at random, Informative missingness, known (and documented) biases, unknown biases, ...	
technical quality	uniqueness	Uniqueness	Uniqueness refers to the degree to which data are not duplicated.	modified Aerts et al., 2021		
technical quality	accuracy	Accuracy	Accuracy refers to the degree to which data correctly describes what it was designed to measure (the "real world" entity).	modified Health Information and Quality Authority, 2018		
technical quality	accuracy	Precision	Precision refers to the degree of approximation by which data can represent reality (e.g. numerical resolution or	modified European Medicines Agency (EMA), 2023		

			the number of categories).			
technical quality	accuracy	Reliability	Reliability refers to how closely does the data reflect what it was designed to measure and is this consistent over time.	modified TEHDAS 6.1, 2022	i.e. the 'temporal stability' of accuracy	
technical quality	accuracy	Method-based accuracy	Method-based accuracy refers to the accuracy of the diagnostic methods used for generating or collecting the data.	modified Eder & Shekhovtsov, 2021	relevant aspect, but possibly hard to define metrics	
technical quality	accuracy	Data falsification	Data falsification refers to the extent to which data values are intentionally falsified or synthesised.	modified Schwabe et al., 2024	specific scope AI: falsified or synthetic data as a feature, not a bug.	
technical quality	validity	Validity	Validity refers to the degree to which representations of data in a dataset conform to internal or external formatting, relational, or computational definitions.	modified Kahn et al., 2016		
technical quality	validity	Syntactic validity	Syntactic validity refers to the degree to which data conforms to the syntax (e.g. format, type, range) of its definition.	modified DAMA UK, 2013		.) The definition proposed originally referring to the data dictionary was rated 2nd. .) The DAMA definition rated 1st, which explicitly refers to some elements of syntax: "Data are valid if it conforms to the syntax (format, type, range) of its definition." --> Given that 'data dictionary' also raised a question which would

						require the additional definition of data dictionary to understand syntactic validity, we propose to use DAMA and modify it for consistent language and allowing for other aspects of syntax in order to generalise for data elements other than 'variables': "Syntactic validity refers to the degree to which data conforms to the syntax (e.g. format, type, range) of its definition."
technical quality	validity	Relational validity	Relational validity refers to the degree to which a dataset conforms to the data model.	modified Kahn et al., 2016		
technical quality	validity	Computational validity	Computational validity refers to the degree to which derived values conform to technical functional specifications.	modified Kahn et al., 2016		
technical quality	timeliness	Timeliness	Timeliness refers to how promptly the data are collected after the point in time they apply to.	modified Health Information and Quality Authority, 2018		
technical quality	timeliness	Currentness	Currentness refers to how close the point in time to which the data apply is to the present.	modified Statistics Finland, 2022		

<p>technical quality</p>	<p>consistency</p>	<p>Consistency</p>	<p>Consistency refers to the degree to which data has attributes that are free from contradiction and are coherent with other data in a specific context of use. It can be either or both among data regarding one entity and across similar data for comparable entities.</p>	<p>modified ISO/IEC 25012</p>	<p>The main aspect is "absence of contradiction". Examples (from Kahn et al 2015) that might be metrics: .) violations of data model cardinality rules. A cardinality rule determines when zero, one, or more than one data row in one table can be linked to one or more data rows in another table. .) violations of data model primary/foreign key rules. A primary/foreign key requires that a row in one table (the foreign key) must point to a row in another table (the primary key). The primary key row must be present. .) violations of cross-variables dependency rules. A cross-variables dependency states that one row can only exist if another row or value exists. For example, the state of pregnancy should exist only if the patient sex is female. .) violations of co-occurrence rules. Systolic and diastolic blood pressures should always occur as a pair. .) Report violations of co-measurement rules (two distinct measurements of the same observation). Age and date of birth should agree. .) Report violations of mutual</p>	<p>The proposed definition (modified ISO) was rated 2nd: "Consistency refers to the degree to which data has attributes that are free from contradiction. This can encompass comparing - representations or instances of one attribute or entity, - several related attributes or entities with each other, - or against definitions or constraints." The original ISO rated 1st: "The degree to which data has attributes that are free from contradiction and are coherent with other data in a specific context of use. It can be either or both among data regarding one entity and across similar data for comparable entities." Considerations were: .) consistent language: "Consistency refers to ..." at the beginning. .) removing the part "and are coherent with other data in a specific context of use", because it seems a bit vague and not adding anything to the much stricter 'free from contradiction'. .) being more explicit about to what data is compared. As both definitions express the same, just in different wordings,</p>
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					<p>exclusivity rules. A patient should not be recorded as being dead and alive at the same time.</p>	<p>while the unmodified version is rated higher and more 'standard', it makes sense to return to the original form. Only the consistent language across dimensions should be kept, therefore we propose to use:</p> <p>"Consistency refers to the degree to which data has attributes that are free from contradiction and are coherent with other data in a specific context of use. It can be either or both among data regarding one entity and across similar data for comparable entities." The source is then still modified ISO/IEC 25012 (but less modified).</p>
technical quality	consistency	Relational consistency	Relational consistency refers to the degree to which data has attributes that are free from relational contradiction, i.e. each entity shall be represented by at most one identifiable data unit, or by multiple but consistent identifiable units.	modified ISO 8000-8:2015		
technical quality	none, we propose plausibility	Plausibility	Plausibility refers to the degree to which data has attributes that are regarded as true and believable by users in a specific context of use, i.e. data agrees with expectations from	modified ISO/IEC 25012		

			internal knowledge like related attributes, or external knowledge like real-world knowledge, literature, etc.			
technical quality	none, we propose plausibility	Plausibility of repeated measurements	Plausibility of repeated measurements means that values of repeated measurement of the same fact show expected variability.	modified Kahn et al., 2016		
technical quality	none, we propose plausibility	Plausibility of state transitions	Plausibility of state transitions means that sequences of values that represent state transitions conform to expected properties.	modified Kahn et al., 2016		
technical quality	none, we propose plausibility	Plausibility of temporal density	Plausibility of temporal density means that measures of data value density against a time-oriented denominator are expected.	modified Kahn et al., 2016		
technical quality	none, we propose coherence	Coherence	Coherence refers to the degree to which aspects relevant for analysability are used consistently throughout a dataset or across different datasets or versions of one dataset. Examples are: - Are formats the same (e.g., of different date variables)? - Is the precision of values the same (e.g., age	modified European Medicines Agency (EMA), 2023	It does not fall under consistency, which aims at contradictions: E.g. When recording start and end dates with different precisions, the data can be perfectly consistent chronologically, but they are not coherent in terms of analysability.	

			<p>always approximated to years)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Are references to entities consistent so that information about the same entity is properly linked across parts of the dataset? 			
technical quality	none, we propose coherence	External coherence	External coherence refers to the degree to which it is possible to combine and make use of related data from different sources based on consistent use of aspects relevant for analysability, such as formats, standards and methods.	modified Health Information and Quality Authority, 2018	some overlap with comparability	
technical quality	none, we propose coherence	Internal coherence	Internal coherence refers to the degree to which it is possible to combine and make use of related data within a dataset based on consistent use of aspects relevant for analysability, such as formats, standards and methods.	modified Health Information and Quality Authority, 2018	some overlap with comparability	
technical quality	none, we propose coherence	Format coherence	Format coherence refers to the degree to which formats are used consistently throughout a dataset or across different datasets or versions of one dataset, improving analysability.	modified European Medicines Agency (EMA), 2023	Sub-dimension' of coherence.	

technical quality	none, we propose coherence	Semantic coherence	Semantic coherence refers to the degree to which the same value means the same throughout a dataset or across different datasets or versions of one dataset, improving analysability.	modified European Medicines Agency (EMA), 2023	Sub-dimension' of coherence.	
technical quality	none, we propose comparability	Comparability	Comparability refers to how the consistent use of definitions, standards and methods facilitates comparison of data.	modified Health Information and Quality Authority, 2018	It is closely related to coherence, but coherence focuses more on the 'compatibility' of different attributes in the context of analysability (often in one dataset), while comparability focuses more on the 'compatibility' of different versions of one attribute, e.g. over time or from different datasets.	
technical quality	none, we propose comparability	Regional comparability	Regional comparability refers to how the consistent use of definitions, standards and methods facilitates comparison of data from different regions or populations.	modified Health Information and Quality Authority, 2018		
technical quality	none, we propose comparability	Temporal comparability	Temporal comparability refers to how the consistent use of definitions, standards and methods facilitates comparison of data over time.	modified Health Information and Quality Authority, 2018		

coverage	representation of multi-disciplinary electronic health data	Multidisciplinary coverage	Multidisciplinary coverage refers to the representation of several disciplines, tiers of the health care system or domains producing health related data.	modified HDR UK Data Utility Framework (Gordon et al, 2021)		
coverage	representativity of population sampled	Population coverage	Population coverage refers to the coverage rate of the population in question.	modified Health Information and Quality Authority, 2018		
coverage	representativity of population sampled	Population representativity	Population representativity refers to the degree to which the data adequately represent the population in question.	modified TEHDAS 6.1, 2022	This differs from population coverage in that it does not only look at the proportion covered, but also on the distributions. E.g. a selection bias might be detected here, that cannot be seen from population coverage alone.	
coverage	average timeframe in which a natural person appears in a dataset	Observation period	Observation period refers to the timeframe in which observed entities (notably natural persons) appear in the dataset.	modified HDR UK Data Utility Framework (Gordon et al, 2021)	Is this dimension actually a metric? E.g. from inclusion to end of follow-up in a clinical study.	
access and provision	time between the collection of the electronic health data and their addition to the dataset	Release timeliness	Release timeliness refers to the lag between the data being collected and added to the dataset.	modified HDR UK Data Utility Framework (Gordon et al, 2021)		
access and provision	time to provide electronic	Access timeliness	Access timeliness refers to the lag between data access application	modified HDR UK Data Utility Framework		

	health data following electronic health data access application approval		approval and access to the dataset.	(Gordon et al, 2021)		
access provision and	none, we propose access	Availability	Availability refers to the degree to which data is present, obtainable and ready for use.	modified Zaveri et al., 2016	Might even be out of scope: any data listed in a metadata catalogue should be available.	
access provision and	none, we propose access	Accessibility	Accessibility refers to the degree to which data are easily obtainable, clearly presented in a way that can be understood and available in a suitable format.	modified Health Information and Quality Authority, 2018		
access provision and	none, we propose access	Use permissiveness	Use permissiveness refers to the degree of permissiveness that licences and requirements for ethical and data governance approval grant to a user for the intended use.	modified HDR UK Data Utility Framework (Gordon et al, 2021)		
data modifications	merging and adding data to an existing dataset	Data merge documentation	Data merge documentation refers to information on data modifications that merged data to an existing dataset.	modified Kahn et al, Table 1. Data Quality Assessment Documentation and Reporting Recommendations, 2015	The differentiation of 'merging' and 'adding' is maybe too specific, and can be summarised under 'adding'.	
data modifications	merging and adding data to an existing	Data addition documentation	Data addition documentation refers to information on data	modified Kahn et al, Table 1. Data Quality		

	dataset	on	modifications that added data to an existing dataset.	Assessment Documentation and Reporting Recommendations, 2015		
data modifications	including links with other dataset	Data linkage documentation	Data linkage documentation refers to information on data modifications that linked other datasets to an existing dataset.	modified Kahn et al, Table 1. Data Quality Assessment Documentation and Reporting Recommendations, 2015		

Glossary

This tab contains commonly used terms from the reviewed literature and their consolidated definition.				
Term	Definition	Source	Poll votes	Comment
Fit for purpose	Fit for purpose refers to the degree to which a dataset is suitable for a particular application or purpose, encompassing factors such as quality, credibility, scale, interoperability, accessibility, cost, format, timeliness etc. Data fits the purposes of the user, which is a post hoc judgement. It may imply the need for collecting users' feedback or users' returns.	modified TEHDAS 6.3, 2023		
Fit for use	Fit for use refers to the suitability of data for the intended use, which is achieved by appropriate data preparation to meet the needs of a data user.	modified TEHDAS 6.3, 2023		
Data quality	'Data quality' means the degree to which the elements of electronic health data are suitable for their intended primary and secondary use.	EHDS regulation, final compromise text, 2024		GÖG: Is this definition binding for the project? The regulations says "for the purposes of this Regulation the following definitions shall apply".

	Data quality is a complex, multidimensional concept that defies a one-size-fits-all description. Data quality is context dependent, which means the same data elements or data sources may be deemed high quality for one use and poor quality for a different use.	Kahn et al., 2015	10	GÖG: This is a true statement, but not a definition, it is an explanation why there is no definition.
	The state of completeness, validity, consistency, timeliness and accuracy that makes data appropriate for a specific use.	DAMA UK, 2024	5	
	Data quality is defined as fitness for purpose for users' needs in relation to health research, policy making and regulation and that data reflect the reality, which they aim to represent.	TEHDAS 6.1, 2022	2	
	Data quality refers to how data fits data users' needs.	TEHDAS 6.3, 2023	2	
	The degree to which the characteristics of a dataset meet requirements or objectives. The suitability of the data for the purpose the data user intends to use the data, and for which the data producer provides the data.	Statistics Finland, 2022	1	
Data utility	Data utility refers to the usefulness of a dataset for a given purpose. It is a user-centric view on data quality, that relies both on a priori and post-hoc conditions of the data. Commonly, a priori conditions can be categorised within the fit-for-use approach in which main data quality dimensions can be assessed to inform about the operational status of the data to be used (or reused). Post-hoc conditions are about fulfilling the expectations of a potential user that are specific to a certain purpose, which follows a fit-for-purpose approach. Utility can be measured using metrics of utilisation (i.e., in how many studies a data set has been exploited), metrics of interest (i.e., how many users has queried the data), or value scores (i.e., how the data user value the data provided).	modified TEHDAS 6.3, 2023 and HDR UK, 2020		
Dataset	'Dataset' means a structured collection of electronic health data.	EHDS regulation, final compromise text, 2024		GÖG: Is this definition binding for the project? The regulations says "for the purposes of this Regulation the following definitions shall apply".
		QUANTUM working definition		

Data dictionary	A data dictionary is a description of data definitions used for data elements, including descriptions of data types and content for each element, links to external standards and resources, and any required context for interpreting data. It focuses on descriptions of what the (representation of) data means.	modified NIH, 2024, CMS, 2021 and UC Merced Library, 2024		
Data model	A data model organises data elements and standardises how the data elements relate to one another. A data model explicitly determines the structure of data, usually in a data modelling notation, which is often graphical in form. This understanding is complemented by a data dictionary, providing detailed descriptions of individual data elements, enhancing data comprehension within the broader data model framework.	modified Princeton University, Center for Data Analytics and Reporting, 2024 and Coursera, 2023		
	A data model organizes data elements and standardizes how the data elements relate to one another. Since data elements document real life people, places and things and the events between them, the data model represents reality. For example a house has many windows or a cat has two eyes. Data models are often used as an aid to communication between the business people defining the requirements for a computer system and the technical people defining the design in response to those requirements. They are used to show the data needed and created by business processes. A data model explicitly determines the structure of data. Data models are specified in a data modelling notation, which is often graphical in form. A data model can be sometimes referred to as a data structure, especially in the context of programming languages. Data models are often complemented by function models.	Princeton University, Center for Data Analytics and Reporting, 2024		
	A data model defines the relationships between data points, useful in software development, data migration and system integration. Data models can be used to design new systems and software. In business intelligence, they can help database architects and data analysts gain insight into company data and its attributes, and set parameters for data grouping, sorting, storing, and formatting.	Coursera, 2023		

Provenance	Provenance is defined as a record that describes the people, institutions, entities, and activities involved in producing, influencing, or delivering a piece of data or a thing. In particular, the provenance of information is crucial in deciding whether information is to be trusted, how it should be integrated with other diverse information sources, and how to give credit to its originators when reusing it. In an open and inclusive environment such as the Web, where users find information that is often contradictory or questionable, provenance can help those users to make trust judgements.	PROV-DM, 2013		
Generation	Generation is the completion of production of a new entity by an activity. This entity did not exist before generation and becomes available for usage after this generation.	PROV-DM, 2013		entity' in the context of provenance, data or data element or dataset in the context of QUANTUM
Derivation	A derivation is a transformation of an entity into another, an update of an entity resulting in a new one, or the construction of a new entity based on a pre-existing entity.	PROV-DM, 2013		entity' in the context of provenance, data or data element or dataset in the context of QUANTUM
Agent	An agent is something that bears some form of responsibility for an activity taking place, for the existence of an entity, or for another agent's activity. Common types of agents are persons, organisations or software agents.	PROV-DM, 2013		entity' in the context of provenance, data or data element or dataset in the context of QUANTUM

Sources

This tab contains reviewed sources.				
Source	Title	Description, what is relevant, ...	Link	CAVE
Aerts et al., 2021	Is the quality of hospital EHR data sufficient to evidence its ICHOM outcomes performance in heart failure? A pilot evaluation	The i~HD (European Institute for Innovation through Health Data) prioritized 9 data quality dimensions as most important to assess the quality of health data	https://www.medrxiv.org/content/10.1101/2021.02.04.21250990v1.full.pdf	

CMS, 2021	A Quick Guide to Data Dictionary		https://www.cms.gov/files/document/data-dictionary-quick-reference-guide.pdf	
Coursera, 2023	What Is a Data Model?		https://www.coursera.org/articles/data-model	
DAMA UK, 2013	THE SIX PRIMARY DIMENSIONS FOR DATA QUALITY ASSESSMENT: Defining Data Quality Dimensions	Dimensions and definitions	https://www.sbctc.edu/resources/documents/colleges-staff/commissions-councils/dgc/data-quality-dimensions.pdf	
DAMA UK, 2024	GLOSSARY OF DATA MANAGEMENT TERMS	Dataset	https://www.dama-uk.org/Glossary	
DCAT v3, 2024	Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT) - Version 3, W3C Recommendation 2024-01-18	DCAT Class Dataset	https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat/#class-dataset	
Declerck et al., 2024	Frameworks, Dimensions, Definitions of Aspects, and Assessment Methods for the Appraisal of Quality of Health Data for Secondary Use: Comprehensive Overview of Reviews	Paper von Jens Declerck von i~HD -> specifically relevant: Table 1 Mapping of data quality aspects (=definitions) labelled the observed definitions of dimensions from the reviews as "aspects" framework of the i~HD served as a reference framework for mapping the diverse literature in the field	https://medinform.jmir.org/2024/1/e51560/PDF	
DPV, 2024	Data Privacy Vocabulary (DPV), version 2		https://w3c.github.io/dpv/dpv/	
DQV		RDF Property qb:dataSet	https://raw.githubusercontent.com/UKGovLD/publishing-statistical-data/master/specs/src/main/vocab/cube.ttl#dataSet	

ECDC, 2014	Data quality monitoring and surveillance system evaluation		https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/sites/default/files/media/en/publications/Publications/Data-quality-monitoring-surveillance-system-evaluation-Sept-2014.pdf	
Eder & Shekhovtsov, 2021	Construction of quality-assured infant feeding process of care data repositories: definition and design (Part 1)	BBMRI	https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/IJWIS-03-2021-0026/full/html	
EHDS regulation, final compromise text, 2024	Proposal for a Regulation on the European Health Data Space - Analysis of the final compromise text with a view to agreement		https://www.consilium.europa.eu/media/70909/st07553-en24.pdf	
European Commission, 2019	Data quality management	This study explores the intersection between data quality management (from a data governance point of view) and semantic interoperability: how semantic assets support and evolve data quality considerations. It describes state of the art concepts and frameworks for data quality and links those to semantic interoperability by studying how data quality can be improved.	https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/document/2019-09/SEMIC%20Study%20on%20data%20quality%20management.pdf	

European Medicines Agency (EMA), 2023	Data Quality Framework for EU medicines regulation	<p>This document is the first release of the EU data quality framework for medicines regulation and addresses high level principles and procedures that apply across the European Medicines Regulatory Network (EMRN)'s regulatory activities. This framework provides general considerations on data quality that are relevant for regulatory decision making, definitions for data dimensions and sub-dimensions, as well as their characterisation and related metrics. It provides an analysis of what data quality actions and metrics can be put in place in different scenarios and introduces a maturity model to drive the evolution of automation to support data-driven regulatory decision making.</p> <p>This document is intended to be an overall umbrella from which more focused recommendations can be derived for specific regulatory domains with specified metrics and checks.</p>	https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/regulatory-procedural-guideline/data-quality-framework-eu-medicines-regulation_en.pdf	
EUROSTAT 2.0, 2019	Quality Assurance Framework of the European Statistical System		https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/documents/64157/4392716/ESS-QAF-V2.0-final.pdf	
FAIRplus, 2024	Glossary terms	Dataset	https://fairplus.github.io/Data-Maturity/docs/Glossary/#dataset	
García-de-León-C hocano et al., 2015	Construction of quality-assured infant feeding process of care data repositories: definition and design (Part 1)		https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0010482515003340?via%3Dihub	

HDR UK Data Utility Framework (Gordon et al, 2021)	Development of a data utility framework to support effective health data curation	Information on the key characteristics related to dataset utility, based on surveys, interviews and testing, were used to provide a standard framework for dataset evaluation according to purpose	https://informatics.bmj.com/content/bmjhci/28/1/e100303.full.pdf	Cave: Appendix - Suggestion/ Updates - https://www.hdr.uk.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/201105-Updates-to-the-Data-Utility-Framework-v2.pdf
HDR UK, 2020	Data Utility Green Paper – Draft for Consultation	Dataset	https://www.hdr.uk.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/200820-Data-Utility-Green-Paper-Consultation-Draft.pdf	
Health Information and Quality Authority (HIQA), 2018	Guidance on a data quality framework for health and social care	The purpose of this document is to provide guidance to health and social care organisations on how to develop a data quality framework, in order to systematically assess, monitor, evaluate and improve the quality of their data and information: They structure it as Dimension > Characteristic > Description p.50 Proposed data dictionary structure p.51 International frameworks reviewed to support guidance for a data and information quality framework for health and social care	https://www.hiqa.ie/sites/default/files/2018-10/Guidance-for-a-data-quality-framework.pdf	
ISO 8000-2:2020			https://cdn.standards.iteh.ai/samples/80543/52a2903758024943b67d346ffb2a64	

			bc/ISO-8000-2-2020.pdf	
ISO 8000-8:2015	Data quality Part 8: Information and data quality: Concepts and measuring			proprietary
ISO/IEC 25012, 2022	ISO/IEC 25012	ISO/IEC 25012	https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dqv/#bib-ISOIEC25012 https://iso25000.com/index.php/en/iso-25000-standards/iso-25012	
Kahn et al., 2012	A Pragmatic Framework for Single-site and Multisite Data Quality Assessment in Electronic Health Record-based Clinical Research	They propose a “fit-for-use” conceptual model for data quality assessment and a process model for planning and conducting single-site and multisite data quality assessments.	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3833692/pdf/nihms522627.pdf	
Kahn et al., 2015	Transparent Reporting of Data Quality in Distributed Data Networks	Recommendations propose reporting on both general and analysis-specific data quality features	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4434997/pdf/egems1052.pdf	
Kahn et al., 2016	A Harmonized Data Quality Assessment Terminology and Framework for the Secondary Use of Electronic Health Record Data	Existing DQ terms were harmonized and organized into a framework by defining three DQ categories	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5051581/pdf/egems1244.pdf	
Kesisoglou et al., 2022	Glossary of commonly used terms in the field of health data research - developed by the EU project HealthyCloud		https://zenodo.org/records/6787119	
Lacagnina et al., 2023	Towards a data quality framework for EOSC		https://www.eosc.eu/sites/default/files/2023-01/Towards_a_data_quality_framework_for_eosc.pdf	
Lee et al., 2017	A Framework for Data Quality Assessment in Clinical Research Datasets	Created an inventory of common phenotype data elements (CPDEs) derived from open-access datasets and evaluated it against the modified DQA framework	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5977591/pdf/2731442.pdf	

Liaw et al., 2021	Quality assessment of real-world data repositories across the data life cycle: A literature review	They sought to complete a literature review on DQ assessment frameworks, indicators and tools for research, public health, service, and quality improvement across the data life cycle.	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8475229/pdf/ocaa340.pdf	
NHS, 2024	NHS NHS Data Model and Dictionary - Data Set		https://www.england.nhs.uk/data-services/validate/	
NIH, 2024	Data Dictionary		https://www.nlm.gov/guides/data-glossary/data-dictionary#:~:text=The%20term%20codebook%20is%20often,the%20structure%20of%20a%20database	
Princeton University, Center for Data Analytics and Reporting, 2024	What is a Data Model?		https://cedar.princeton.edu/understanding-data/what-data-model	
PROV-DM, 2013	PROV-DM: The PROV Data Model	This document introduces the provenance concepts found in PROV and defines PROV-DM types and relations. The PROV data model is domain-agnostic, but is equipped with extensibility points allowing domain-specific information to be included.	https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-dm/	
PROV-O, 2013	PROV-O: The PROV Ontology		https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/	
Quantum T2.1 Survey, 2024	T2.1 Survey results from Vincent Blanes Selva		https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/IJWIS-03-2021-0026/full/pdf?title=data-quality-for-federated-medical-data-lakes	
Sáez et al., 2012	Organizing Data Quality Assessment of		https://ebooks.iospress.nl/p	

	Shifting Biomedical Data		ublication/21838	
Schmidt et al., 2021	Facilitating harmonized data quality assessments. A data quality framework for observational health research data collections with software implementations in R	The presented data quality framework is the first of its kind for observational health research data collections that links a formal concept to implementations in R. The framework and tools facilitate harmonized data quality assessments in pursue of transparent and reproducible research. -> also in APHP slides	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8019177/pdf/12874_2021_Article_1252.pdf	
Schwabe et al., 2024	The METRIC-framework for assessing data quality for trustworthy AI in medicine: a systematic review	The systematic comparison of previous studies on data quality combined with the perspective on modern ML enables us to develop a specialised data quality framework for medical training data: the METRIC-framework. It provides a comprehensive list of 15 awareness dimensions which developers of AI medical devices should be mindful of.	https://arxiv.org/pdf/2402.13635.pdf	
Statistics Finland, 2022	Data quality criteria and indicators – a proposal for a recommendation	Data Quality Framework, TiHA WP3	https://stat.fi/media/uploads/org/tiedon-laatukehikko/data_quality_criteria_and_indicators - a proposal for a recommendation.pdf	
TEHDAS 6.1, 2022	European Health Data Space Data Quality Framework	Deliverable 6.1 This report explores and synthesizes the existing knowledge and experiences on data quality frameworks (DQFs) in the context of cross-border sharing of federated secondary use health data with the aim to identify good practice within this area and make recommendations. -> 4.1.3 Data Quality Dimension at Data Source Level -> 4.1.4 Data Quality Dimension at the Institution level	https://tehdas.eu/app/uploads/2022/05/tehdas-european-health-data-space-data-quality-framework-2022-05-18.pdf	

TEHDAS 6.3, 2023	Recommendations on a Data Quality Framework for the European Health Data Space for secondary use	Deliverable 6.3	https://tehdas.eu/app/uploads/2023/09/tehdas-recommendations-on-a-data-quality-framework.pdf	deleted
UC Merced Library, 2024	What Is a Data Dictionary?		https://library.ucmerced.edu/data-dictionaries	
Weiskopf & Weng, 2012	Methods and dimensions of electronic health record data quality assessment: enabling reuse for clinical research	review the methods and dimensions of data quality assessment in the context of electronic health record (EHR) data reuse for research	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3555312/pdf/amiainl-2011-000681.pdf	
Zaveri et al., 2016	Quality assessment for Linked Data: A Survey		https://www.semantic-web-journal.net/system/files/swj773.pdf	

Annex 2 - Milestone report 1.2

M1.2 Consensus process for a data quality and utility label

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Dissemination Level	N/A
QUANTUM summary	QUANTUM aims at developing and implementing a label mechanism that could be ideally adopted in the future HealthData@EU. QUANTUM builds on 5 technical work packages (WP). WP1 conceptualises and provides technical specifications for a data quality, utility, and maturity label. WP2 designs and tests, at small-scale, the label. WP3 implements the labelling mechanism in a number of data holders. WP4 engages the data quality users' community; and, WP5 outreaches other interested parties, including other initiatives building HealthData@EU.
Deliverable abstract	N/A
Keywords	Delphi, data quality label, data quality dimension, RAND/UCLA method

QUANTUM CONSORTIUM			
#	Short Name	Organisation Name	Country
1	IACS	INSTITUTO ARAGONÉS DE CIENCIAS DE LA SALUD	ES

2	Sciensano	SCIENSANO	BE
3	Health Data Hub	PLATEFORME DES DONNEES DE SANTE	FR
3.1	HOSPICES LYON	HOSPICES CIVILS DE LYON	FR
3.2	HOSP TOULOUSE	CENTRE HOSPITALIER UNIVERSITAIRE DE TOULOUSE	FR
3.3	CHU Bordeaux	CHU HÔPITAUX DE BORDEAUX	FR
4	I-HD	THE EUROPEAN INSTITUTE FOR INNOVATION THROUGH HEALTH DATA	BE
5	UCSC	UNIVERSITÀ CATTOLICA DEL SACRO CUORE	IT
6	BBMRI-ERIC	BIOBANKS AND BIOMOLECULAR RESOURCES RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE CONSORTIUM	AT
7	DIGITALEUROPE	DIGITALEUROPE AISBL	BE
8	GÖG	GESUNDHEIT OSTERREICH GMBH	AT
9	UPV	UNIVERSITAT POLITECNICA DE VALENCIA	ES
10	HEALTH-RI	STICHTING HEALTH-RI	NL
11	EUHA	EUROPEAN UNIVERSITY HOSPITAL ALLIANCE	BE
12	AP-HP	ASSISTANCE PUBLIQUE HÔPITAUX DE PARIS	FR
13	VIB	VIB VZW	BE
14	CIPH	HRVATSKI ZAVOD ZA JAVNO ZDRAVSTVO	HR
15	HUS	HUS-YHTYMA	FI
16	THL	TERVEYDEN JA HYVINVOINNIN LAITOS	FI
17	ECRIN	ECRIN EUROPEAN CLINICAL RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE NETWORK	FR
18	BFARM	BUNDESINSTITUT FÜR ARZNEIMITTEL UND MEDIZINPRODUKTE	DE
19	HIQA	HEALTH INFORMATION AND QUALITY AUTHORITY	IE
20	ISS	ISTITUTO SUPERIORE DI SANITÀ	IT
21	CESSDA ERIC	CESSDA ERIC	NO
21.1	KNAW	KONINKLIJKE NEDERLANDSE AKADEMIE VAN WETENSCHAPPEN - KNAW	NL
21.2	EKKE	ETHNIKO KENTRO KOINONIKON EREVNON	EL
22	e-helse	DIREKTORAT FOR E-HELSE	NO
23	U.PORTO	UNIVERSIDADE DO PORTO	PT
24	SPMS	SERVIÇOS PARTILHADOS DO MINISTÉRIO DA SAÚDE EPE	PT
25	NIJZ	NACIONALNI INSTITUT ZA JAVNO ZDRAVJE	SI
26	ERASMUS MC	ERASMUS UNIVERSITAIR MEDISCH CENTRUM ROTTERDAM	NL
27	EDHA	EUROPEAN DIGITAL HEALTH ACADEMY GGMBH	DE
28	HDR UK	HEALTH DATA RESEARCH UK	UK
29	UESSEX	UNIVERSITY OF ESSEX	UK
30	INSERM	INSTITUT NATIONAL DE LA SANTÉ ET DE LA RECHERCHE MÉDICALE	FR

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QUANTUM
THE HEALTH DATA QUALITY LABEL

Developing a data quality and utility label for the European Health Data Space.

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

AI	The Asymmetry Index
CFA	Correction Factor for Asymmetry
DQ	Data Quality
EHDS	European Health Data Space
HDAB	Health Data Access Body

IPRAS	Interpercentile Range Adjusted for Symmetry
IPRCP	Interpercentile Range Central Point
IPR	Interpercentile Range

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1 Introduction

The present study corresponds to the Milestone 1.2 of the QUANTUM EU project.

The QUANTUM project proposes a data quality, utility and maturity labelling approach for datasets of data holders in the European Health Data Space (EHDS, 2024) that allows data users and health data access body (HDAB) to access and use data in an optimal and trustworthy manner through information about their quality and utility aspects for specific purposes.

The specific objectives of QUANTUM are the following:

- 1) Conceptualise and develop a data quality and utility label system embedded in a data holder maturity model;
- 2) Develop and test tools for the labelling of the data sets' quality and utility and data holders' maturity;
- 3) Analyse the implementation challenges to enable the transferability and sustainability of the labelling mechanism as part of HealthData@EU;
- 4) Develop a capacity-building and outreach program that allows a broad engagement with the data quality-wide community.

Task 1.2 is part of the first objective and builds upon the results from Task 1.1, which involved an extensive and systematic literature review along with individual expert consultations. This was also coupled with a synthesis of the data quality frameworks identified in the literature review to avoid overlaps and to provide consistent and reliable definitions for each dimension within their respective categories. This process produced a set of 54 data quality (DQ) dimensions, which were the input for Task 1.2. Therefore, after Task 1.1 identified the most determinant and representative dimensions for the health domain, this set was transformed into a Delphi process. The goal is to achieve consensus on the most relevant and priority dimensions for evaluating the quality and utility of datasets, thereby aiding in the development of a data quality, utility, and maturity labelling tool.

2 Methodology

Before diving into the methodologies used for the Delphi study, it is pivotal to assess and describe also the methods used in Task 1.1 since, as described in the introduction, it represents the basis on which this study was built. This initial task involved an extensive literature review and expert consultation aimed at identifying the most relevant data quality dimensions. The process began with source selection, drawing on project calls, the Grant Agreement, expert knowledge, and surveys among project partners to select pertinent sources. This selection was further extended by systematically searching databases such as Google Scholar and PubMed using keywords like "Data Quality Framework", "Data Quality Label", "Data Quality

Dimensions”, “Data Quality Metrics”, “Data Utility”, and “Data Quality Criteria”. Inclusion criteria focused on English-language sources that provided systematic approaches to data quality, particularly within the health data field.

Following source selection, data extraction was performed to gather categories, subcategories, dimensions, subdimensions, characteristics, and definitions from the identified sources. A common language was established to ensure consistency in terms like “Fit for Purpose/Use”, “Data Quality”, “Data Utility”, and “Dataset”. The extracted data underwent a thorough consolidation process, which included harmonizing the hierarchy of elements, addressing spelling and terminology inconsistencies, removing duplicates, and refining the scope of each dimension. This process also involved aligning the dimensions with EHDS Categories and Elements, selecting the best-suited definitions, and harmonizing language across dimensions.

The resulting list of 54 quality dimensions, organized into five EHDS categories and 24 EHDS elements, was further refined through feedback mechanisms. Open discussions, surveys, and expert interviews were conducted to finalize the definitions and ensure the dimensions were fit for purpose. This consolidated list formed the conceptual map that served as the substrate for the Delphi study, which aimed to achieve consensus on the relevance and priority of these dimensions using the RAND/UCLA method.

The RAND/UCLA Appropriateness Method (RAM) is a systematic approach used to combine scientific evidence with the collective judgement of experts to determine the appropriateness of specific healthcare procedures. Developed in the 1980s by the RAND Corporation and UCLA researchers, this method has become widely utilised in the field of healthcare, particularly for assessing the overuse, underuse, or misuse of medical and surgical procedures (Fitch et al., 2001).

This method was selected for this study due to its effectiveness in combining quantitative and qualitative data to reach a consensus in complex scenarios. It is particularly suited for the current task because it provides a rigorous and systematic approach to evaluating expert opinions, ensuring that the process is both comprehensive and unbiased. It is designed to handle variability in expert ratings and identify areas of agreement and disagreement, making it ideal for evaluating the relevance and priority of multiple data quality dimensions. In the present scenario, it was employed to systematically analyse expert ratings of ‘n’ data quality (DQ) dimensions using a 9-point Likert scale (Kravitz et al., 1995).

The Interpercentile Range (IPR) was used to measure the spread or dispersion of ratings within a distribution, specifically between the 30th and 70th percentiles. Moreover, this measure will be used in a later stage to assess the level of agreement among participants. This approach captures the central tendency of ratings while ignoring extreme values, providing a clearer picture of the general consensus among panellists. The calculation of IPR involved determining the 30th percentile (lower percentile) and the 70th percentile (upper percentile) of the data. The IPR is then derived as the difference between these percentiles:

$$IPR = upper_{percentile} - lower_{percentile}$$

Subsequently, the **Interpercentile Range Central Point (IPRCP)** was calculated. The IPRCP represents the midpoint of the IPR and is computed as follows:

$$IPRCP = \frac{upper_{percentile} + lower_{percentile}}{2}$$

The **Asymmetry Index (AI)** was introduced to account for the deviation of the central point of the IPR from the midpoint of the scale, typically 5 on a 1-9 scale:

$$AI = 5 - IPRCP$$

The **IPRAS (Interpercentile Range Adjusted for Symmetry)** was then calculated to adjust for the symmetry of the distribution around the midpoint of the scale. This adjustment is necessary to account for any asymmetry in the distribution of ratings, making the measure more robust.

The formula used is:

$$IPRAS = |IPR_R + (AI * CFA)|$$

Where:

- IPR_r represents the **baseline IPR** under perfect symmetry and is a constant (2.35);
- **The Correction Factor for Asymmetry (CFA)** is also a constant value (CFA = 1.5) which adjusts the IPR based on the asymmetry index.

For each DQ dimension, the median rating was calculated to identify the central tendency of the panellists' opinions. The 9-point Likert scale was segmented into three ranges: **1-3 indicating rejection, 4-6 indicating uncertainty, and 7-9 indicating acceptance**. The position of the median within these ranges guided the initial inclination towards acceptance, rejection, or uncertainty. To further refine the analysis, the IPR was calculated, and its value was adjusted using the IPRAS formula. If the actual IPR exceeded the IPRAS, it indicated disagreement among the panellists.

Based on the median position and the level of agreement, three scenarios for decision-making were defined:

- If the median fell within the 7-9 range and IPR was less than or equal to IPRAS, the DQ dimension was accepted;
- If the median was within the 1-3 range and IPR was less than or equal to IPRAS, the DQ dimension was rejected;
- If the median was in the 4-6 range or if there was disagreement (IPR greater than IPRAS) in the other two scenarios, the DQ dimension was moved to the second round for further deliberation.

The RAND/UCLA Appropriateness Method was chosen for this study due to its structured framework, which allows for a rigorous analysis of expert opinions. By focusing on the IPR and adjusting for symmetry with IPRAS, this method effectively handles variability in ratings and distinguishes between genuine consensus and disagreement. The clear scenarios for acceptance, rejection, and further deliberation provide practical guidance for decision-making, ensuring that the most relevant and prioritized dimensions are retained. This approach ensures a robust and transparent evaluation process, forming a solid foundation for developing a comprehensive data quality labelling tool for the European Health Data Space (Fitch et al., 2001).

Using the median instead of the mean is particularly advantageous in this context. The median is less sensitive to outliers, providing a more accurate central tendency when expert opinions vary widely. Likert scales, being ordinal, are better suited to median calculations because the median does not assume equal intervals between scale points, unlike the mean. This makes the median a more appropriate and interpretable measure for the consensus-building process inherent in the Delphi method (Hasson et al., 2000).

In addition to the quantitative assessment, a **qualitative assessment** of the comments received from participants was conducted. As described in the next subsection 2.1, in the Welphi platform, participants could write comments on each DQ dimension to provide their inputs. Special attention was given to comments on dimensions that lacked agreement. Two researchers independently analysed the comments, classifying them into various categories based on topic and relevance to consensus. Their findings were presented to the coordination team and other researchers to assess whether the final output pointed in the same direction.

Finally, in each round, dimensions were displayed according to EHDS categories specified in Article 56 (European Commission, 2024), with dimensions under the same category being displayed on separate screens, raising the possibility of inducing an anchoring effect. This effect could lead participants to perceive dimensions within the same category as equivalent, potentially influencing them to score both relevance or priority within the category similarly, rather than just focusing on relevance. Similarly, this effect could also lead participants to “anchor” their expectations to the first screen, constantly under-evaluating or over-evaluating subsequent categories.

To investigate this, a visual analysis was performed through a **box plot and a ridge plot** of the categories to assess any substitution effects that might arise from participants using mixed criteria during scoring. The box plot illustrates the distribution of ratings by category, accounting for the median, interquartile range (IQR), and outliers. The ridge plot displays density curves representing the distribution of ratings for a specific EHDS category. The height and shape of the curve indicate the concentration of ratings. It is important to look for differences in the peak positions, widths, and shapes of the curves. If the curves for different categories have distinct shapes or peaks, it suggests that participants rated the dimensions in these categories differently. Concerning the anchoring effects, if the distributions for categories that appear later in the survey are skewed differently compared to earlier

categories, it might suggest anchoring effects.

To further assess the presence or not of anchoring effect, a statistical test called **ANOVA** (one-way in this specific context) was carried out. This test is conducted twice, first comparing the mean of the ratings across different categories and then comparing the mean of median scores of each category against the mean median score of all dimensions combined. The first one determines if there are statistically significant differences in the mean ratings given by participants across different EHDS categories. The second approach determines if the median ratings (central tendency) of each category significantly differ from one another and from the overall median rating of all dimensions combined.

It is important to look at both approaches because **the mean rating analysis** focuses on the average ratings, which can be influenced by outliers and the overall distribution of ratings. While, **the median scores analysis** focuses on the central tendency of ratings, providing a robust measure less sensitive to outliers.

2.1 Welphi platform outlook

In conducting the Delphi study, a preliminary detailed market analysis of various Delphi platforms was performed to identify the most suitable tool for the task needs. The analysis considered Smart Delphi, Welphi, and eDelphi, evaluating each platform against a comprehensive set of criteria related to question customisation, analysis capabilities, pricing, respondent management, and user experience. Based on this evaluation, Welphi was selected as the optimal platform. Below are outlined the specific reasons for this choice.

Welphi offers extensive capabilities for customising questions, which is crucial for the Delphi method. It supports various Likert scales, allowing the response options to be tailored to specific requirements. Additionally, Welphi enables commenting on each item, providing an avenue for qualitative feedback that complements the quantitative ratings. The platform also enhances readability by displaying item definitions contextually, avoiding clutter in the question text.

Another significant advantage of Welphi is its ability to group questions into blocks and clusters without limitations, unlike Smart Delphi, which imposes a maximum of 60 items per cluster. This flexibility is essential for organizing the questions logically. Furthermore, Welphi can deliver questions in randomised order, reducing potential response biases and ensuring the reliability of the collected data.

Welphi's analysis capabilities are also a decisive factor in its selection. The platform allows for the export of data to statistical software and provides aggregated statistics, facilitating a comprehensive analysis of the Delphi rounds. This functionality makes it easier to summarise and interpret the results.

Respondent management is another area where Welphi excels. The platform allows for

tracking responses, generating personalised email links, and creating different profiles for expert groups. This capability ensures effective management of participant engagement and data collection. Additionally, Welphi includes a standardised informed consent process, enhancing ethical compliance and ensuring that participants are fully informed about the study's purpose and procedures.

The Welphi survey for the Delphi study on data quality dimensions was structured to guide participants systematically through each stage of the evaluation process.

The survey commenced with a **Welcome Message** page, where participants were introduced to the purpose of the survey and provided with initial instructions.

Following this, the **Informed Consent** page ensured that all participants were fully informed about the nature of the study and consented to their participation.

Subsequently, the survey included a section on **Participant Categorization** to gather professional background information, allowing for a nuanced understanding of the participant pool. Similarly, an additional categorization page was presented: **Participant's Categorization - With Regard to the EHDS**, distinguishing between Data Users, Data Holder, and Data Access Body.

The **Dataset Definition** page provided the definition of a dataset with examples based on the HealthDCAT-AP definition, ensuring a consistent understanding among all participants.

The survey then proceeded to **the core sections**, where participants evaluated various Data Quality dimensions organised per EHDS categories. Hence, the DQ dimensions within a specific category were presented in a separate screen. These sections included Data Documentation, Technical Quality, Coverage, Access and Provision, and Data Modifications. The survey concluded with a Thank You Message Page.

The Delphi consultation was specifically targeted to known stakeholders and data quality experts, although participation was open to any stakeholder via invitation from a partner participating in the QUANTUM-CSA. The aim was to ensure adequate representation of the different roles involved in the EHDS (i.e., HDAB, Data holders, Data users).

Below (**Figure 1**) is reported an example of how the DQ dimensions were presented to the participants. By clicking on the eye symbol, it was possible to read the definition of the related dimension, while by clicking on the comment icon on the right side, participants could leave a comment.

	Dettagli	1 - Not relevant at all	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9 - Absolutely relevant	Commento
Multidisciplinary coverage											
Temporal coverage											
Population coverage											
Population representativity											
Observation period											

Figure 1 - Delphi Platform

3 First round results

This section describes the general results and the selection process of each DQ dimension performed in the first round of the Delphi analysis. Sub-sections 3.1 to 3.7, provide a more technical and detailed examination of the various facets that make up the current analysis and results.

The initial round of the Delphi consultation was centred on evaluating **the relevance** of the presented dimensions. The participants were presented with the following question while evaluating each DQ dimension: “*If you were to decide on the quality and utility of a dataset. How RELEVANT would you consider the following dimensions, on a scale from 1 (Not relevant at all) to 9 (Absolutely relevant)?*”. The first round achieved a satisfactory level of participation, with 109 participants adequately representing all the different roles involved in the European Health Data Space. The total number of experts contacted was 648 (participation rate 17%).

The results from the first round were analysed using the RAND-modified Delphi methodology, which relies on median scores and levels of agreement determined by the Interpercentile Range (IPR). The synthesis of the literature from data quality frameworks (Task 1.1) ensured that all dimensions were considered relevant at baseline, which led to a distribution skewed towards higher scores (7-9). This necessitated an adjustment of the threshold, focusing on the significance of the lack of agreement as per the RAND-modified Delphi criteria, using IPR to assess the level of agreement.

Therefore, for the second round, it was decided to drop the dimensions **lacking agreement** ($IPR > IPRAS$) in the first round and only dimensions with high levels of agreement and the highest median scores were retained.

In addition to the quantitative assessment, a qualitative assessment of the comments received from participants was conducted. Special attention was given to comments on dimensions that lacked agreement. This qualitative analysis supported the decision to drop certain dimensions based on the lack of agreement.

The analysis on the anchoring effect revealed some differences in the distribution of the mean category scores. However, no statistically significant differences were found in the median score distribution. Consequently, potential anchoring effects were considered negligible based on these findings.

3.1 Selection Criteria and Process

Based on the information provided in Section 3, out of 54 dimensions, 34 dimensions (**Table 1**) reached the level of agreement (IPRAS>IPR) and obtained a median score in the top segment (7-9) while 20 DQ dimensions did not reach the necessary agreement level with an IPR greater than IPRAS (**Table 3**). The comment analysis performed on these 20 dimensions confirmed the lack of agreement and the overlap of some of these dimensions with the other 34 dimensions part of the accepted group. Below are the lists of dimensions that were accepted (or not) and in **Table 2** are displayed the statistics for the 34 dimensions that passed to the second round.

Table 1 - 34 Data Quality Dimensions accepted

34 Data Quality Dimensions accepted			
1	Metadata granularity	18	Relational validity
2	Data dictionary granularity	19	Computational validity
3	Compliance	20	Consistency
4	Data origin provenance	21	Relational consistency
5	Data derivation provenance	22	Coherence
6	Traceability	23	Internal coherence
7	Trustworthiness	24	Format coherence
8	Data model granularity	25	Semantic coherence
9	Completeness	26	Comparability
10	Capture completeness	27	Temporal comparability
11	Data completeness	28	Temporal coverage
12	Accuracy	29	Population coverage
13	Precision	30	Population representativity
14	Reliability	31	Availability
15	Data falsification	32	Accessibility
16	Validity	33	Use permissiveness
			Data linkage documentation
17	Syntactic validity	34	

Table 2 - Statistics of the 34 accepted dimensions

DQ Dimension	Median	Mean	Std_Dev	Lower Percent.	Upper Percent.	IPR	IPRAS	IQR	Segment
Metadata granularity	8	7.55	1.63	7	9	2	2.15	2	7-9
Data dictionary granularity	8	7.39	1.66	7	9	2	2.15	2	7-9
Compliance	8	7.29	1.67	7	8	1	1.4	2.75	7-9

Data origin provenance	7	7.20	1.61	7	8	1	1.4	1.75	7-9
Data derivation provenance	7	6.86	1.79	6	8	2	0.65	2	7-9
Traceability	7	6.74	1.83	6	8	2	0.65	2	7-9
Trustworthiness	8	7.38	1.84	7	9	2	2.15	2	7-9
Data model granularity	7	7.09	1.69	6.5	8	1.5	1.025	2	7-9
Completeness	8	7.88	1.12	7.5	9	1.5	2.525	2	7-9
Capture completeness	7	6.55	1.65	6	7	1	0.1	2.75	7-9
Data completeness	7.5	7.39	1.22	7	8	1	1.4	1	7-9
Accuracy	8	7.85	1.32	8	9	1	2.9	2	7-9
Precision	7	7.24	1.37	7	8	1	1.4	1	7-9
Reliability	8	7.77	1.35	7.5	9	1.5	2.525	2	7-9
Data falsification	7	6.86	2.07	6	8	2	0.65	3	7-9
Validity	8	7.88	1.20	7	9	2	2.15	2	7-9
Syntactic validity	8	7.44	1.51	7	8	1	1.4	1.75	7-9
Relational validity	8	7.23	1.61	7	8	1	1.4	2	7-9
Computational validity	7	6.94	1.71	6.5	8	1.5	1.025	2	7-9
Consistency	8	7.89	1.16	7	9	2	2.15	2	7-9
Relational consistency	8	7.39	1.58	7	8	1	1.4	2	7-9
Coherence	8	7.67	1.40	7	9	2	2.15	2	7-9
Internal coherence	8	7.27	1.64	7	8	1	1.4	1	7-9
Format coherence	7	7.03	1.64	7	8	1	1.4	2	7-9
Semantic coherence	8	7.53	1.65	7	9	2	2.15	2	7-9
Comparability	7	7.38	1.51	7	8	1	1.4	2	7-9
Temporal comparability	7	7.09	1.72	7	8	1	1.4	2	7-9
Temporal coverage	7	6.98	1.42	6	8	2	0.65	2	7-9
Population coverage	8	7.17	1.77	7	8	1	1.4	1.75	7-9
Population representativity	8	7.77	1.33	7	9	2	2.15	2	7-9
Availability	8	7.45	1.70	7	9	2	2.15	2	7-9
Accessibility	8	7.68	1.44	7	9	2	2.15	2	7-9

Use permissiveness	7.5	7.17	1.89	7	8	1	1.4	2	7-9
Data linkage documentation	7	7.03	1.75	6.5	8	1.5	1.025	2.75	7-9

Table 3 - 34 Data Quality Dimensions not accepted

20 Data Quality Dimensions not accepted			
1	Support documentation granularity	11	Plausibility of state transitions
2	Mapping completeness	12	Plausibility of temporal density
3	Provenance granularity	13	External coherence
4	Data agency provenance	14	Regional comparability
5	Uniqueness	15	Multidisciplinary coverage
6	Method-based accuracy	16	Observation period
7	Timeliness	17	Release timeliness
8	Currentness	18	Access timeliness
9	Plausibility	19	Data merge documentation
10	Plausibility of repeated measurements	20	Data addition documentation

3.2 Level of agreement by participant role

The focus of the analysis here is on the participant role (i.e. Data holder, Data user, Data access body), showing the percentage of participants per role (**Figure 2**) and their level of agreement within each segment.

The data holders had the highest role participating in the survey, followed by the data users category which reached almost the same percentage. While the proportion of health access bodies was 22% of the total.

Table 4 below represents the level of agreement per role and segment. The segment 4-6 shows the lowest agreement level among all the roles showing indeed uncertainty in the relevance of the related dimensions. While in the top segment which houses on average 50 dimensions, has a more consistent level of agreement with the data holder and data user having similar and the highest levels of agreement (70% and 69% respectively). Although the level of agreement is slightly lower for the health access bodies (53%), it still indicates a majority consensus on the high relevance of these dimensions.

Figure 2 - distribution of participants

Role	N	N%
Data holder	44	40%
Data User	41	38%
HDAB	24	22%
TOTAL	109	100%

Table 4 - Level of agreement per role & segment

Segment	EHDS Category	Level of agreement	Min & Max	Dimension Number	Dimensions
1-3	Data User	-	-	0	<i>no dimension</i>
	Data Holder	-	-	0	no dimension

	Data Access body	-	-	0	no dimension
4-6	Data User	0%	Min 1 & Max 9	2	"Currentness", "Multidisciplinary coverage"
	Data Holder	33%	Min 1.33 & Max 9	3	2up + "Release timeliness"
	Data Access body	0%	Min 2 & Max 8.6	5	3up + "Plausibility of state transition", "Regional comparability"
7-9	Data User	69%	Min 2.82 & Max 9	52	The remaining
	Data Holder	70%	Min 2.84 & Max 9	51	The remaining
	Data Access body	53%	Min 3.1 & Max 9	49	The remaining

3.3 Level of agreement by segment

In this subsection, it is delineated the level of agreement within each segment by determining the instances where IPRAS is greater than IPR. Additionally, it identifies the number of dimensions and the minimum and maximum values for each segment, providing insight into the range of responses.

For 34 dimensions, the Interquartile Range Acceptable Score (IPRAS) exceeded the Interquartile Range (IPR). This indicates a high level of agreement among the experts for these dimensions.

Conversely, for 20 dimensions, the IPRAS was smaller than the IPR. This implies a lower level of agreement among the experts, as the acceptable range of variability was less than the observed variability, indicating more divergent opinions among the experts.

Furthermore, the distribution of dimensions across different segments based on their median values was analysed. The vast majority of dimensions (96.3%) fell within segment 7-9, signifying a strong consensus on the high relevance of these dimensions. This observation is further reinforced by the fact that most dimensions had a median score of 8. Only two dimensions were categorized within the segment 4-6, and none fell within the segment 1-3. This distribution underscores the overall high relevance attributed to the dimensions by the experts. These results are presented in **Table 5** which provides a summary of the distribution of dimensions across these segments, highlighting the central tendency and variability in expert ratings. The segment 1-3 has no dimensions, while segment 4-6 has only two dimensions but no

agreement with an IPR greater than IPRAS, hence both dimensions are part of the 20 that have been discarded. While the majority of dimensions (52) fall into the last segment.

Table 5 - Dimensions distribution

Segment	N dim (votes)	% N dim	Dimensions	IPRAS > IPR (level of agreement)	Min & Max
1-3	0	-	-	-	-
4-6	2	3.7%	"Currentness" "Multidisciplinary coverage"	0%	1 min – 9 max (for both DQ dim)
7-9	52	96.3%	All the rest	65%	1.96 min – 9 max

3.4 Frequency of Comments per Dimensions

Tables 4 and 5 show the number of comments per DQ dimension divided into two main groups: Accepted dimensions (34) and rejected ones (20).

Table 6 - Frequency of comments in the Accepted Dimensions

	Accepted DQ dimensions	
	dimensions	N comments
1	Accessibility	2
2	Accuracy	4
3	Availability	2
4	Capture completeness	5
5	Coherence	2
6	Comparability	4
7	Completeness	5
8	Compliance	7
9	Computational validity	8
10	Consistency	5
11	Data completeness	8
12	Data derivation provenance	7
13	Data dictionary granularity	7
14	Data falsification	3
15	Data linkage documentation	7
16	Data model granularity	7
17	Data origin provenance	5
18	Format coherence	2
19	Internal coherence	3
20	Metadata granularity	3
21	Population coverage	6
22	Population representativity	6

23	Precision	5
24	Relational consistency	5
25	Relational validity	6
26	Reliability	3
27	Semantic coherence	4
28	Syntactic validity	3
29	Temporal comparability	6
30	Temporal coverage	5
31	Traceability	7
32	Trustworthiness	9
33	Use permissiveness	6
34	Validity	5
	mean	5.35
	standard deviation	2.32

Table 7 - Frequency of comments in the Rejected Dimensions

	Rejected DQ dimensions	
	dimensions	N comments
1	Access timeliness	3
2	Currentness	2
3	Data addition documentation	2
4	Data agency provenance	6
5	Data merge documentation	4
6	External coherence	4
7	Mapping completeness	2
8	Method-based accuracy	1
9	Multidisciplinary coverage	7
10	Observation period	7
11	Plausibility	6
12	Plausibility of repeated measurements	3
13	Plausibility of state transitions	8
14	Plausibility of temporal density	8
15	Provenance granularity	7
16	Regional comparability	5
17	Release timeliness	8
18	Support documentation granularity	6
19	Timeliness	9
20	Uniqueness	7
	mean	6.75
	standard deviation	2.85

The mean number of comments for the rejected dimensions is higher (6.75) compared to the accepted dimensions (5.35), suggesting more discussion or contention around these

dimensions. This is in line with the qualitative analysis conducted on the comments of the rejected dimensions. Both researchers agreed that their findings were aligned on the lack of agreement and on several comments about overlaps with other dimensions (in the accepted list), the latter being perceived as more important and/or better suited to represent this dimension. With a lower frequency, some comments also pointed to the fact that the relevance of certain dimensions varies depending on the context, type of work, or specific use cases. Finally, other comments pointed to unclear definitions or scarcity of examples, which could lead to a higher frequency of comments due to confusion.

3.5 Sentiment Analysis and Categorization of Participant Comments

In this study, to aid the analysis of the comments made by the two researchers, a **sentiment analysis** together with a **topic clustering** was conducted on the comments of the rejected dimensions. The analysis aimed to categorize the comments based on predefined categories to ensure that any nuance and input were captured in those dimensions kept for the second round. After identifying the main “comment categories” it was also evaluated the sentiment associated with each category.

The initial step involved loading the comments from an Excel file using the pandas library. The comments underwent a pre-processing phase to clean the text, where non-alphabetic characters were removed, text was converted to lowercase, tokenized, and stop words were eliminated. Additionally, stemming was applied to reduce words to their root forms using the nltk library.

Following pre-processing, an initial keyword analysis identified the most common terms and phrases within the comments. A categorization dictionary was then constructed, encompassing themes such as '*definition clarity*', '*examples needed*', '*relevance*', '*overlap with other dimensions*', '*context dependence*', '*specificity*', '*justification*', '*usefulness*', and '*confusion*'. Each comment was classified into these categories based on the presence of relevant keywords. The distribution of comments across these categories was visualized using a count plot to provide an overview of their prevalence.

Sentiment analysis was performed using pre-trained models from VADER and TextBlob, generating sentiment scores for each comment on a scale from -1 (very negative) to 1 (very positive). The overall distribution of sentiment scores was plotted (**Figure 3**) with a histogram with a kernel density estimate (KDE) overlay to discern general sentiment trends across the comments. As expected, the most prominent feature is the large spike at the sentiment score of 0, which suggests that the majority of comments were neutral in tone.

Figure 3 - Distribution of Sentiment Scores

Following the sentiment analysis and classification of comments, a **summary of the sentiment scores** for each category was generated. The table of summary statistics (**Figure 4**) provides mean, median, and standard deviation values for sentiment scores across the different comment categories. As highlighted already by the histogram, the average sentiment of participants commenting on each DQ dimension is neutral, showing a moderate approach in describing the entity under examination.

Summary Statistics for Sentiment Scores by Category:				
	Comment_Category	mean	median	std
0	confusion	-0.125000	-0.125000	0.176777
1	context_dependence	0.067599	0.000000	0.192898
2	definition_clarity	0.073699	0.000000	0.161298
3	examples_needed	0.131865	0.100000	0.150939
4	justification	0.173417	0.130167	0.187757
5	other	0.042106	0.000000	0.208003
6	overlap_with_other_dimensions	0.044361	0.000000	0.104007
7	specificity	0.212269	0.293750	0.267014
8	usefulness	0.345556	0.400000	0.258962

Figure 4 - summary statistics

The below box plot (**Figure 5**) shows the distribution of sentiment scores for each comment

category. It helped in visualizing the range, median, and presence of outliers for sentiment scores in each category. It is possible to note that only the "confusion" category has a slightly negative sentiment score (below zero). This aligns with the sentiment of feeling confused by the unclear definition and thus slightly frustrated. Conversely, the "usefulness" category, which encompasses comments that find the evaluated DQ dimension useful, has the highest sentiment score. This aligns with the expectation that individuals exhibit more positive sentiments towards something they find useful, thereby confirming that the overall analysis accurately captured the sentiment. In general, the overall categories display neutral sentiment scores (around zero), which is consistent with a context like the Delphi method, characterized by objective and scholarly discourse.

In conclusion, the sentiment analysis coupled with the comment categorization aligns with the decision taken by the two independent researchers, where the topics covered by the discarded dimensions are either not relevant, or already encapsulated in the dimensions accepted and moved to the second round.

Figure 5 - Distribution of Sentiment Scores by Category

3.6 EHDS categories analysis and anchoring effect

In each round, dimensions were displayed by category, which might have induced an anchoring effect. As detailed in the methodology section, density plots and ANOVA tests were conducted to examine this potential effect. The actual section presents the findings from these analyses, highlighting any deviations in the mean and median scores across categories.

Table 8 shows the behaviour of the 54 DQ dimensions organised under various EHDS (European Health Data Space) categories in terms of relevancy and agreement. Looking at the mean and median of medians there is no clear pattern of systematic under- or over-evaluation of the subsequent categories after the first one (anchoring effect), which is an initial positive sign. In regard to the statistics of this table, the Access and provision category shows moderate agreement with high relevance, indicating general consensus on its importance despite some variability. Similarly, the Coverage category also shows moderate agreement and a slightly lower relevance score. The Data documentation and Technical quality categories exhibit the highest agreement, suggesting better consensus and strong relevance. In contrast, the Data Modifications category has the lowest agreement, indicating variability and less consensus, though its relevance score remains high.

Table 8 - Results per EHDS category

EHDS Category	Agreement Percentage	Mean of Medians	Median of Medians
Access and provision	60%	7.6	8
Coverage	60%	7.2	8
Data documentation	66.67%	7.7	8
Data modifications	33.33%	7.3	7
Technical quality	65.52%	7.7	8

In addition to Table 8, various types of analyses (reported below) have been performed to assess the presence of anchoring effects. Specifically, for a visual comparison, the box plot (**Figure 6**) and the ridge plot (**Figure 7**) were computed to compare the distribution of ratings. This approach is useful to examine the central tendencies across screens and to look for patterns where ratings in earlier screens might influence ratings in subsequent screens.

The visual analysis of the box plot below (**Figure 6**) indicates that the dimensions presented within each category on separate screens generally have high relevance scores, which may suggest a potential influence but there is not a clear pattern. Moreover, the variability in agreement percentages suggests that while the presentation might anchor relevance scores, there is still diversity in participant opinions on specific dimensions.

Figure 6 - Distribution of Ratings by Category

The above findings are confirmed by the **Figure 7** below representing a ridge plot. It is notable that the highest concentration is around 8-9 with some longer tails. However, the effect is not strong enough to be considered impactful since there is not a clear consistent pattern between the first screen and the rest.

Figure 7 - Ridge Plot

This is also confirmed by the statistical analysis below (one-way ANOVA test) which reveals no statistically significant difference in the distribution of median scores.

1st ANOVA test: $F=5.4818$, $p=0.00021$

2nd ANOVA test: **F=0.6729, p=0.6139**

The F-Statistic (5.48) indicates that there is more variance between the group means than within the groups. This suggests that the mean ratings across the different EHDS categories are significantly different from each other. While, the P-value (0.0002) is much lower than the typical significance threshold of 0.05, indicating that the differences in mean ratings across categories are statistically significant. This significance may indeed show some effect in the ordering choice where the first category could anchor the expectations of the participants.

However, the results from the second test and the non-significant of the latter reduce this potential effect noticeably. The F-Statistic of 0.67 indicates that there is less variance between the group medians than within the groups. This suggests that the mean of the median scores across the different EHDS categories are not significantly different from each other. While, a P-value of 0.614 is much higher than the typical significance threshold of 0.05, indicating that the differences in the mean of the median scores across categories are not statistically significant.

In conclusion, the significant ANOVA results indicate that participants rated categories differently, showing that there were inherent differences in how categories were perceived. The non-significant results from the median scores analysis suggest that the central tendency of the ratings was more robust and less influenced by order effects, which is the measure used to assess the acceptance decision for each dimension together with the level of agreement.

4 Second round results

After having identified 34 data quality dimensions as the most **relevant** in assessing the quality and utility of health data, the aim of the second round was to prioritize these dimensions by **weighting their importance** in terms of valuing the quality and utility of a dataset. This round had an adequate level of participation with 66 out of 109 initial participants (a 39.44% drop-off) and adequately represented all the different roles involved in the EHDS. The outputs were analysed using the same methodology as the first round, comparing median scores and agreement levels based on IPR and IPRAS indices.

For dimensions that did not reach consensus on priority in this second round, the decision was made not to exclude them, given their relevance and the high agreement observed in the initial round. These dimensions were classified as '**recommended or optional**' for implementation in the QUANTUM label tool and will not influence the quality scoring or ranking criteria of the tool.

Additionally, as per the first round, a qualitative assessment of participant comments on dimensions lacking priority consensus was performed. Both researchers agreed that their findings were aligned with the decision to leave those categories as optional and out of the scope of the quality scoring or ranking criteria to be implemented as the QUANTUM label.

4.1 Selection Criteria and Process

The below **Figure 8** shows a table with the 34 dimensions passed from the first round. Out of them, 26 reached an adequate level of agreement considering them relevant and priority. While 8 dimensions had an IPR greater than their IPRAS with also the lowest mean, therefore not reaching the desired level. These 8 dimensions are highlighted in the table and are the ones that will be considered “recommended or optional”. The table also shows other informative statistics such as the max and min value reached per each dimension, the standard deviation (Std_Dev) of the average vote and the interquartile range (IQR) calculated as the difference between the 75th percentile and the 25th percentile. Finally, also for the second round, all the dimensions were rated in the top segment (7-9) denoting their importance and relevance (shown in Table 4).

DQ_Dimension	Median	Mean	Std_Dev	Lower_P	Upper_P	IPR	IPRAS	IQR	Min	Max	Segment	Decision
Metadata granularity	8	7.55	1.63	7	9	2	2.15	2	1	9	7-9	Accepted
Data dictionary granularity	8	7.39	1.66	7	9	2	2.15	2	2	9	7-9	Accepted
Compliance	8	7.29	1.67	7	8	1	1.4	2.75	1	9	7-9	Accepted
Data origin provenance	7	7.20	1.61	7	8	1	1.4	1.75	3	9	7-9	Accepted
Data derivation provenance	7	6.86	1.79	6	8	2	0.65	2	1	9	7-9	('IPRAS<IPR, median:', 7.0)
Traceability	7	6.74	1.83	6	8	2	0.65	2	2	9	7-9	('IPRAS<IPR, median:', 7.0)
Trustworthiness	8	7.38	1.84	7	9	2	2.15	2	2	9	7-9	Accepted
Data model granularity	7	7.09	1.69	6.5	8	1.5	1.025	2	2	9	7-9	('IPRAS<IPR, median:', 7.0)
Completeness	8	7.88	1.12	7.5	9	1.5	2.525	2	5	9	7-9	Accepted
Capture completeness	7	6.55	1.65	6	7	1	0.1	2.75	1	9	7-9	('IPRAS<IPR, median:', 7.0)
Data completeness	7.5	7.39	1.22	7	8	1	1.4	1	3	9	7-9	Accepted
Accuracy	8	7.85	1.32	8	9	1	2.9	2	3	9	7-9	Accepted
Precision	7	7.24	1.37	7	8	1	1.4	1	3	9	7-9	Accepted
Reliability	8	7.77	1.35	7.5	9	1.5	2.525	2	3	9	7-9	Accepted
Data falsification	7	6.86	2.07	6	8	2	0.65	3	1	9	7-9	('IPRAS<IPR, median:', 7.0)
Validity	8	7.88	1.20	7	9	2	2.15	2	4	9	7-9	Accepted
Syntactic validity	8	7.44	1.51	7	8	1	1.4	1.75	1	9	7-9	Accepted
Relational validity	8	7.23	1.61	7	8	1	1.4	2	1	9	7-9	Accepted
Computational validity	7	6.94	1.71	6.5	8	1.5	1.025	2	1	9	7-9	('IPRAS<IPR, median:', 7.0)
Consistency	8	7.89	1.16	7	9	2	2.15	2	5	9	7-9	Accepted
Relational consistency	8	7.39	1.58	7	8	1	1.4	2	2	9	7-9	Accepted
Coherence	8	7.67	1.40	7	9	2	2.15	2	3	9	7-9	Accepted
Internal coherence	8	7.27	1.64	7	8	1	1.4	1	2	9	7-9	Accepted
Format coherence	7	7.03	1.64	7	8	1	1.4	2	2	9	7-9	Accepted
Semantic coherence	8	7.53	1.65	7	9	2	2.15	2	2	9	7-9	Accepted
Comparability	7	7.38	1.51	7	8	1	1.4	2	2	9	7-9	Accepted
Temporal comparability	7	7.09	1.72	7	8	1	1.4	2	2	9	7-9	Accepted
Temporal coverage	7	6.98	1.42	6	8	2	0.65	2	4	9	7-9	('IPRAS<IPR, median:', 7.0)
Population coverage	8	7.17	1.77	7	8	1	1.4	1.75	1	9	7-9	Accepted
Population representativity	8	7.77	1.33	7	9	2	2.15	2	3	9	7-9	Accepted
Availability	8	7.45	1.70	7	9	2	2.15	2	1	9	7-9	Accepted
Accessibility	8	7.68	1.44	7	9	2	2.15	2	3	9	7-9	Accepted
Use permissiveness	7.5	7.17	1.89	7	8	1	1.4	2	1	9	7-9	Accepted
Data linkage documentation	7	7.03	1.75	6.5	8	1.5	1.025	2.75	3	9	7-9	('IPRAS<IPR, median:', 7.0)

Figure 8 - 34 DQ Dimensions 2nd Round

Table 9 - Dimension distribution

Segment	N dim	% N dim
1-3	0	0%
4-6	0	0%
7-9	34	100%

4.2 Level of agreement by participant role

The focus of the analysis here is on the participant role (i.e. Data holder, Data user, Data access body), showing the percentage of participants per role (**Figure 9**) and their level of agreement within each segment.

Similar to the first round, the Data holder had the highest role participating in the survey, followed by the Data user, while the proportion of the Data access body was 23% of the total.

Figure 9 - distribution of participants

Participant role	N	N%	1st round N	1st round N%
Data holder	30	45%	44	40%

Data User	21	32%	41	38%
HDAB	15	23%	24	22%
TOTAL	66	100%	109	100%

Table 10 displays the level of agreement per segment and participant role. Only two dimensions were rated in the segment 4-6 and for only one category (Data users) without however reaching a minimum level of agreement. All the other dimensions are clustered in the top segment with the Data access body touching the highest level of agreement (85.3%) followed by Data holder (73.5%) and then Data user (62.5%).

Table 10 - Level of agreement per segment & participant role

Segment	Participant role	Level of agreement	Min & Max	Dimension Number
1-3	Data User	-	-	0
	Data Holder	-	-	0
	Data Access body	-	-	0
4-6	Data User	0%	2 - 8.5	2
	Data Holder	-	-	0
	Data Access body	-	-	0
7-9	Data User	62.5%	Min 3.28 & Max 8.97	32
	Data Holder	73.53%	Min 2.97 & Max 9	34
	Data Access body	85.3%	Min 4.41 & Max 9	34

4.3 Level of agreement by segment

This subsection identifies the level of agreement within each segment by determining the

instances where IPRAS is greater than IPR. Additionally, it displays the minimum and maximum values for each segment (Table 11).

Table 11 - Level of agreement per segment

Segment	Number of votes	IPRAS > IPR (level of agreement)	Min & Max
1-3	0	-	-
4-6	0	-	-
7-9	34	76.5%	2.24 min – 9 max

In Table 11 segments 1-3 and 4-6 have no dimensions, hence there are no related data. While all the dimensions (34) fall into the last segment, indicating high relevance (median values between 7 and 9). The level of agreement is significantly high in this segment, with 76.5% of the dimensions having IPRAS greater than IPR. The min and max difference is high but most of the values are clustered around 8.

4.4 Frequency of Comments per Dimensions

Tables 12 and 13 show the number of comments per DQ dimension divided into two main groups: rejected dimensions (8) and accepted dimensions (26). The mean number of comments for the rejected dimensions is higher (mean 4.86) compared to the accepted dimensions (mean 2.65), suggesting more discussion or contention around these dimensions.

Table 12 - Comment frequency for rejected dimensions

REJECTED	
dimensions	N comments
1 Data derivation provenance	7
2 Traceability	6
3 Data model granularity	5
4 Capture completeness	3
5 Data falsification	10
6 Computational validity	1
7 Temporal coverage	2
8 Data linkage documentation	0
mean	4.86
standard deviation	3.13

Table 13 - Comment frequency for accepted dimensions

ACCEPTED		
	Dimension	N Comments
1	Accessibility	2
2	Accuracy	2
3	Availability	4
4	Coherence	3
5	Comparability	4
6	Completeness	2
7	Compliance	6
8	Consistency	2
9	Data completeness	1
10	Data dictionary granularity	4
11	Data origin provenance	2
12	Format coherence	2
13	Internal coherence	1
14	Metadata granularity	4
15	Population coverage	2
16	Population representativity	1
17	Precision	1
18	Relational consistency	1
19	Relational validity	2
20	Reliability	2
21	Semantic coherence	1
22	Syntactic validity	1
23	Temporal comparability	3
24	Trustworthiness	9
2		
5	Use permissiveness	3
2		
6	Validity	4

mean	2.65	
standard deviation	1.83	

As introduced in section 4, a qualitative assessment of participant comments on dimensions lacking priority consensus was performed. For these dimensions, it was analysed both the comments received during the first and second rounds. The same setting of the first round was replicated, where two researchers conducted the qualitative analysis independently in parallel, classifying the comments into several categories referencing topic and relevance for consensus. The output was presented to the coordination and both researchers agreed that

their findings were aligned with the decision to leave those categories as optional and out of the scope of the quality scoring or ranking criteria to be implemented as the QUANTUM label.

4.5 EHDS categories analysis and anchoring effect

In each round, dimensions were displayed by category, which might have induced an anchoring effect. As detailed in the methodology section, visual analyses and ANOVA tests were conducted to examine this potential effect. The actual section presents the findings from these analyses, highlighting any deviations in the mean and median scores across categories.

Starting with the visual analysis, the box plot below (**Figure 10**) illustrates the distribution of ratings by category, accounting for the median, interquartile range (IQR), and outliers.

Despite the varying number of dimensions, the box plot does not provide strong evidence of anchoring effects. The medians are relatively the same across categories, except for "Data modification" which has a slightly lower median. This difference is more plausible due to the diverse range of dimensions rather than the presentation order. Outliers and the spread of ratings in "Technical quality" reflect variability in participant opinions rather than a systematic bias from anchoring.

Figure 10 - Distribution of Ratings by Category

Table 11 shows numerically what is displayed by the box plot, describing the behaviour of the 34 data quality dimensions organised under EHDS categories in terms of priority and

agreement.

Table 14 - Result per EHDS category

EHDS Category	N of dimensions	Agreement Percentage	Mean of Medians	Median of Medians
Access and provision	3	100%	7.83	8.0
Coverage	3	66.66%	7.66	8.0
Data documentation	8	62.5%	7.5	7.5
Data modifications	1	0%	7.0	7.0
Technical quality	19	84.21%	7.6	8.0

The ridge plot below (**Figure 11**) shows the distribution of ratings across the EHDS categories. Despite the varying number of dimensions, the ridge plot does not show a clear pattern of anchoring. The variation in density is more likely attributed to the variation in the number of dimensions rather than the order of presentation. Categories with fewer dimensions (like "Access and provision" and "Data modifications") show narrower peaks due to less data. In contrast, "Technical quality," with 19 dimensions, has a more spread-out density distribution.

Figure 11 - Ridge Plot

As introduced before, to further assess the presence or not of anchoring effect it was performed the statistical test called ANOVA (one-way in this specific context).

The first ANOVA test yielded the following results: **F=2.13, p=0.074**.

The F-statistic of 2.13 indicates that there is some variation in the mean ratings across the different EHDS categories. The F-statistic measures the ratio of the variance between the

group means to the variance within the groups. A higher F-value would indicate a greater disparity among the group means relative to the within-group variance. The p-value of 0.0746 is slightly above the conventional significance threshold of 0.05. This means that we do not have strong evidence to reject the null hypothesis at the 5% significance level. The null hypothesis in this context is that there are no differences in the mean ratings across the EHDS categories.

Since the p-value is greater than 0.05, we fail to reject the null hypothesis. This suggests that there is no statistically significant difference in the mean ratings across the different EHDS categories. Therefore, based on this ANOVA result, there is no strong evidence to conclude that an anchoring effect is present in the ratings given by participants. However, the reduction in the sample number may have affected the significance of the p-value.

The second one-way ANOVA test yielded the following results for the medians: **F=0.62, p=0.65.**

The F-statistic of 0.62 is quite low, indicating very little variance between the group means relative to the variance within the groups. This suggests that the median ratings across the EHDS categories are very similar to each other. This is confirmed by the box plot displayed before and the overall rating attitude. The p-value of 0.65 is well above the conventional significance threshold of 0.05, failing to reject the null hypothesis. This indicates that there is no statistically significant difference in the median ratings across the different EHDS categories.

Therefore, based on this ANOVA result, there is no evidence to suggest the presence of an anchoring effect in the median ratings given by participants.

The low F-statistic and high p-value together suggest that the central tendencies (medians) of the ratings for each category are consistent and do not show significant variation. This reinforces the conclusion that the presentation order of categories does not seem to have influenced the participants' ratings in terms of central tendency.

5 Discussion

This section discusses several critical points related to the process and findings from Task 1.2.

The conceptual map formed the foundation for identifying and evaluating data quality dimensions. Task 1.1 involved an extensive literature review and expert consultations to ensure all relevant data quality and utility concepts were included in the survey. This thorough approach aimed to cover the breadth of data quality dimensions comprehensively. However, the depth and inclusivity of the background literature review are pivotal for capturing all pertinent concepts, and continuous updates and validations against emerging literature may further enhance this comprehensiveness.

As discussed and addressed in this document, one of the challenges encountered was **the potential ambiguity of certain data quality concepts**. Clear and precise definitions were

crucial to ensure that all participants had a consistent understanding of each dimension, thereby reducing variability in their responses. This ambiguity was addressed through detailed definitions and the opportunity for participants to comment on each dimension, which provided valuable qualitative feedback for refining these concepts.

Another aspect successfully addressed is the anchoring effect, where the sequence of presenting categories might influence participants' ratings. Statistical analyses, including ANOVA tests, were conducted to investigate this potential bias. While the results showed some differences in mean scores across categories, no significant anchoring effect was found on the median scores. This suggests that while presentation order might influence initial impressions, the overall consensus on the central tendency of ratings remained stable.

Another important aspect to consider is **the representativeness of the respondents**, which is critical for the generalizability of the findings. The distribution of roles among data holders, data users, and data access bodies was fairly balanced, which is essential for ensuring that the perspectives of all key stakeholders are considered. Despite the drop-off rate between the first and second rounds, the representativeness across the entire process was maintained. Ensuring consistent participation from all groups is vital for the robustness of the final consensus.

In regard to methodological considerations, the choice of **the modified RAND/UCLA method** for the Delphi process was justified by its structured framework, which combines both quantitative and qualitative data to reach a consensus. This method is well-suited for handling variability in expert ratings and distinguishing between genuine consensus and disagreement. While alternative methods might have produced different results, the RAND/UCLA method's robustness and systematic approach provided a reliable foundation for this study. Furthermore, the decision to use a 9-point Likert scale, as opposed to a 7 or 5-point scale, was based on the need for a finer granularity in capturing expert opinions. A 9-point scale allows for more nuanced responses, which can be particularly valuable in a consensus-building process. This approach aligns with the complexity and diversity of the data quality dimensions being evaluated, providing a detailed and sensitive measure of expert judgments.

6 Conclusion

The successful completion of Milestone 1.2 in the QUANTUM EU project has established a robust consensus process for evaluating data quality and utility dimensions within the European Health Data Space. By employing the RAND/UCLA Appropriateness Method and a two-round Delphi modified process, 34 dimensions were identified as the most relevant of the 54 initially conceived. Afterwards, thanks to the second round, these dimensions were refined by focusing on the highest-priority ones, identifying 26 DQ dimensions with a high level of agreement on their relevance and prime role in assessing the quality and utility of a dataset.

The overall analysis showed high levels of consensus, with no significant anchoring effects observed. The rigorous methodology and comprehensive stakeholder engagement ensure that these identified dimensions will provide a reliable foundation for building an efficient tabling tool as well as for the subsequent task 1.3. The next goal, encapsulated in task 1.3, is to reach

consensus first on the definition of each DQ dimension, and then on how to measure them. This will be reached thanks to a face-to-face nominal group with expert scientists properly representing every category involved in the landscape of the European Health Data Space.

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Annex 3 - Nominal group concept note

QUANTUM: data quality and utility label

Brussels, 4th and 5th of July

The QUANTUM quality and utility label

The dataset labelling mechanism in QUANTUM is meant to respond to the labelling requirements provided in the HealthData@EU legislation (See article 56 [here](#)). The label will be part of the meta-data describing HealthData@EU datasets when catalogued.

Defining a label requires a common understanding of what quality and utility means; particularly, when the challenge is to provide a concept that is agnostic to types of data and purposes.

QUANTUM has opted for setting up a formal consensus process, based on robust consensus methodologies, to achieve this common concept.

The QUANTUM Nominal Group

The nominal group is a qualitative methodology meant to reach consensus on complex topics in a short period of time. The subjects of the nominal group are usually experts relevant to the topic of interest.

The QUANTUM nominal group is meant to **make decisions on the metrics of quality and utility**, once two rounds of consensus have selected quality and utility dimensions according to their relevance and the level of priority to build a label specification.

The list of experts is available [here](#)

Some hints for the nominal group

- This is a directed-discussion group - brainstorming is limited
- Consensus-making is based on an even distribution of speaking time between participants
- Activities will build upon the others - no steps can be skipped
- Transparency in decisions is the rule
- Important roles:
 - The conductor has special rights and cannot be challenged, unless an expert opinion is provided;
 - The rapporteurs take notes and help the conductor to get consensus;
 - The observers cannot speak and help the conductor to reach the objectives.

This nominal group is not covering

Fit-for-purpose: QUANTUM understands fit-for-purpose as a consequence of the actual use of a particular dataset and has to reflect the user's experience for his/her particular purpose.

Data holders maturity: maturity represents the data holders' capacity to manage data and data quality. This is a property of the data holder, not of the datasets.

This nominal group is covering

Quality: defined by a number of dimensions agreed in the first round of the Delphi survey and prioritised in the second round.

Potential utility or fit-for-use: defined by a number of dimensions agreed in the first round of the Delphi survey and prioritised in the second round.

Metrics: experts will be asked to get agreement on

- 1) What potential **measures** quantify each of the dimensions prioritised in the Delphi survey;
- 2) What **operational definitions** would be appropriate for those measures;
- 3) What **values** those measures should take;
- 4) What **thresholds** should be used to report on the quality and utility of a dataset.

Preparation and home work

You are getting this document because you have been invited to be part of the nominal group. You are a domain expert; you do not need to learn about the topic.

As we need you to be prepared for the nominal group, **we kindly ask you to:**

- 1) You are provided a table with the 26 dimensions for which there is substantial agreement on their relevance, and which have been prioritised to take part of the label specification. In the table, those dimensions are sorted by the agreement reached in terms of priority (highest on top). **Read the definitions provided and consider the need for clarification.**

Category	Dimension	Definition (as is)
Technical quality	Accuracy	Accuracy refers to the degree to which data correctly describes what it was designed to measure (the "real world" entity).
Technical quality	Completeness	Completeness refers to the degree to which all required information is present in a particular dataset.
Technical quality	Reliability	Reliability refers to how closely the data reflect what it was designed to measure and is this consistent over time.
Technical quality	Consistency	Consistency refers to the degree to which data has attributes that are free from contradiction and are coherent with other data in a specific context of use. It can be either or both among data regarding one entity and across similar data for comparable entities.
Technical quality	Validity	Validity refers to the degree to which representations of data in a

Category	Dimension	Definition (as is)
		dataset conform to internal or external formatting, relational, or computational definitions.
Coverage	Population representativity	Population representativity refers to the degree to which the data adequately represent the population in question.
Access and provision	Accessibility	Accessibility refers to the degree to which data is easily obtainable, clearly presented in a way that can be understood and available in a suitable format.
Technical quality	Coherence	Coherence refers to the degree to which aspects relevant for analysability are used consistently throughout a dataset or across different datasets or versions of one dataset. Examples: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Are formats the same (e.g., of different date variables)? - Is the precision of values the same (e.g., age always approximated to years)? - Are references to entities consistent so that information about the same entity is properly linked across parts of the dataset?
Data documentation	Metadata granularity	Metadata granularity refers to the availability, comprehensiveness and level of detail of metadata that help users understand the data being used.
Technical quality	Semantic coherence	Semantic coherence refers to the degree to which the same value means the same throughout a dataset or across different datasets or versions of one dataset, improving analysability.
Access and provision	Availability	Availability refers to the degree to which data is present, obtainable and ready for use.
Data documentation	Data dictionary granularity	Data dictionary granularity refers to the availability, comprehensiveness and level of detail of the data dictionary.
Data documentation	Trustworthiness	Trustworthiness refers to the degree to which context information fosters trust in the data, e.g. by documenting agents involved in the provenance of data, data validation routines, the provenance of available provenance information etc.
Technical quality	Syntactic validity	Syntactic validity refers to the degree to which data conforms to the syntax (e.g. format, type, range) of its definition.
Technical quality	Relational consistency	Relational consistency refers to the degree to which data has attributes that are free from relational contradiction, i.e. each entity shall be represented by at most one identifiable data unit, or by multiple but consistent identifiable units.
Data documentation	Compliance	Compliance refers to the degree to which data has attributes that adhere to standards, conventions or regulations in force and similar rules relating to data quality in a specific context of use.
Technical quality	Internal coherence	Internal coherence refers to the degree to which it is possible to combine and make use of related data within a dataset based on consistent use of aspects relevant for analysability, such as formats, standards and methods.
Technical quality	Relational validity	Relational validity refers to the degree to which a dataset conforms to the data model.
Coverage	Population coverage	Population coverage refers to the coverage rate of the population in question.
Technical quality	Data	Data completeness refers to the degree of data attributes being

Category	Dimension	Definition (as is)
	completeness	present in a dataset without reference to specific data values.
Access and provision	Use permissiveness	Use permissiveness refers to the degree of permissiveness that licenses and requirements for ethical and data governance approval grant to a user for the intended use.
Technical quality	Comparability	Comparability refers to how the consistent use of definitions, standards and methods facilitates comparison of data.
Technical quality	Precision	Precision refers to the degree of approximation by which data can represent reality (e.g. numerical resolution or the number of categories).
Data documentation	Data origin provenance	Data origin provenance means a description of the source of the original or raw data prior to any subsequent processing or transformation, including context, purpose, method and technology of data generation.
Technical quality	Temporal comparability	Temporal comparability refers to how the consistent use of definitions, standards and methods facilitates comparison of data over time.
Technical quality	Format coherence	Format coherence refers to the degree to which formats are used consistently throughout a dataset or across different datasets or versions of one dataset, improving analysability.

2) You are kindly asked to warm up. Please, **think of** (and keep for the discussion in Brussels) **operational definitions for the measurement of each dimension in the table**. An operational definition is something similar to: number of variables with missing values; documentation of the population covered by the dataset; percentage of attributes with error; etc. It may be more than one per dimension.

WE DO NOT WANT YOU TO SEND US YOUR THOUGHTS; WE WILL USE THEM LIVE

The discussion timeline

As said, the nominal group is a steered discussion to get agreement on a number of questions in a short period of time. We are all obliged to thoroughly follow the plan as follows:

Step	Slot	Action
1	Presentation of the nominal group	Slides
2	Context: the final goal is a catalogue	Mockup
3	Context: briefing of Delphi results	3 slides
4	Discussion on definitions	Disambiguation if needed
BREAK: Rapporteurs prepare the list of dimensions with the new definitions		
5	Providing weights to dimensions	Auction live - allocate 100 tokens
6	Open brainstorming	Commenting the results on screen

BREAK: We all need a rest		
7	Operational measures (definitions)	Texting on screen and +1 voting
8	Operational measures	Listing / Disambiguating / Merging
BREAK: Rapporteurs prepare the list of measures in a single table		
9	Agreement on measures	Voting live measure by measure
10	Agreement on values	Confirmatory: nodding is enough
11*	Weighting the measures within dimension	Even or voting live
12*	Label reporting of the dataset	Even or voting uneven thresholds

(*) 11 and 12 can be done online the week after

What's next

We will need an extra-effort from your side. You will be invited to **ratify the results** of the nominal group **within the two weeks after**.

After your ratification, the Conductor, Rapporteurs and Observers will have several discussion sessions to get a final report that will be released as the Quality and Utility Specification.

Annex 4 - Online survey for agreement on data dimension measures

I. Accessibility

(Definition of the dimension: Accessibility refers to the dataset being accompanied by clear and transparent access and usage conditions.)

- Accessibility - Measure #1:

- **Definition:** Availability of a data access & usage policy at the time of release of the dataset
- **Value range:**
 - 0: No policy available
 - 1: Basic policy available
 - 2: Comprehensive policy available
- **Recommended measurement approach:** Preferably using a standard vocabulary as for example the DCAT property dct:accessRights

Q1: Do you agree with this measure (definition and value range) to be used as part of the quality and fit-for-use labelling of a dataset in the context of HealthData@EU?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Strongly disagree Strongly agree

Q2 : (non-mandatory): Would you suggest a different approach ?

- Accessibility - Measure #2:

- **Definition:** Number of publications per year using the dataset
- **Value range:** number per year
- **Recommended measurement approach:** Standard publication persistent identifier as for example DOI or URI

Q1 : Do you agree with this measure (definition and value range) to be used as part of the quality and fit-for-use labelling of a dataset in the context of HealthData@EU?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Strongly disagree Strongly agree

Q2 (non-mandatory): Would you suggest a different approach?

- Accessibility - Measure #3:

- **Definition:** Average time from data access application to data release for a specific dataset
- **Value range:**
 - 0: More than 6 months
 - 1: 3 to 6 months
 - 2: 1 to 3 months
 - 3: Less than 1 month
- **Recommended measurement approach:** The HDAB/data holder to provide the average using digital time-stamps for the process

Q1: Do you agree with this measure (definition and value range) to be used as part of the quality and fit-for-use labelling of a dataset in the context of HealthData@EU?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9
Strongly disagree Strongly agree

Q2 (non-mandatory): Would you suggest a different approach?

II. Population coverage

(Definition of the dimension: Population coverage refers to the degree to which a dataset includes the potential eligible population.)

- Population coverage - Measure #1:
 - **Definition:** Coverage Rate (percentage of the eligible population represented in the dataset)
 - **Value range:**
[0-1] (percentage)
<80%: Limited coverage
80-90%: Good coverage
90-95%: Very good coverage
95-100%: Near-universal or universal coverage
 - **Recommended measurement approach:** According to data holder information: (Number of individuals in the dataset / Total eligible population)

Q1: Do you agree with this measure (definition and value range) to be used as part of the quality and fit-for-use labelling of a dataset in the context of HealthData@EU?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9
Strongly disagree Strongly agree

Q2 (non-mandatory): Would you suggest a different approach?

III. Population representativity

(Definition of the dimension: Population representativity refers to the degree to which the data adequately represent the population in question.)

- Population representativity - Measure #1:
 - **Definition:** How closely does the observed population match the expected population?
 - **Value range:**
0: No information of method of collection
1: Non representative sample
2: Representative sample
3: Universe of data
 - **Recommended measurement approach:** According to data holder's

information

Q1: Do you agree with this measure (definition and value range) to be used as part of the quality and fit-for-use labelling of a dataset in the context of HealthData@EU?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9
Strongly disagree Strongly agree

Q2 (non-mandatory): Would you suggest a different approach?

IV. Compliance

(Definition of the dimension: Compliance refers to the degree to which data has attributes that adhere to ethical standards, conventions, protocols or regulations.)

- Compliance - Measure #1:
 - **Definition:** Is there an ethical approval number or a similar reference associated with this dataset?
 - **Value range:**
 - 0: No
 - 1: No, but an explanation is given, why this is not applicable
 - 2: Yes
 - **Recommended measurement approach:** According to data holder's information, in the case of (1) possibly referring to relevant regulation

Q1: Do you agree with this measure (definition and value range) to be used as part of the quality and fit-for-use labelling of a dataset in the context of HealthData@EU?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9
Strongly disagree Strongly agree

Q2 (non-mandatory): Would you suggest a different approach?

- Compliance - Measure #2:
 - **Definition:** Is there documentation of compliance with ethical standards, conventions, protocols or regulations?
 - **Value range:**
 - 0: No.
 - 1: Documentation of applicable ethical standards, conventions, protocols or regulations, but no documentation of deviations or compliance.
 - 2: Documentation of applicable ethical standards, conventions, protocols or regulations, as well as documentation of deviations or compliance.
 - **Recommended measurement approach:** According to data holder's information.

Q1: Do you agree with this measure (definition and value range) to be used as part of the quality and fit-for-use labelling of a dataset in the context of HealthData@EU?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Strongly disagree Strongly agree

Q2 (non-mandatory): Would you suggest a different approach?

V. Data provenance

(Definition of the dimension: Data provenance means a description of the source of the data, including context, purpose, method and technology of data generation, documenting agents involved in the provenance of data, data validation routines, source data verification, traceability of changes, and quality control of data.)

- Data provenance - Measure #1:
 - **Definition:** Is the source of the dataset documented?
 - **Value range:**
 - 0: no data available
 - 1: data is available
 - **Recommended measurement approach:** Ideally using a standard vocabulary as in DCAT-AP "dct:source; dct:creator; dct:contributor"

Q1: Do you agree with this measure (definition and value range) to be used as part of the quality and fit-for-use labelling of a dataset in the context of HealthData@EU?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Strongly disagree Strongly agree

Q2 (non-mandatory): Would you suggest a different approach?

- Data provenance - Measure #2:
 - **Definition:** Is traceability documented?
 - **Value range:**
 - 0: No documentation of provenance
 - 1: Some documentation of provenance not complying with agent, activity and derivation standards
 - 2: Full documentation of provenance complying with agent, activity and derivation standards
 - **Recommended measurement approach:** Ideally using a standard vocabulary as in PROV-D

Q1: Do you agree with this measure (definition and value range) to be used as part of the quality and fit-for-use labelling of a dataset in the context of HealthData@EU?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Strongly disagree Strongly agree

Q2 (non mandatory) : Would you suggest a different approach ?

VI. Metadata Scope

(Definition of the dimension: Metadata scope refers to the availability, comprehensiveness, level of detail of metadata and data dictionary that help users understand the data being used.)

- Metadata scope - Measure #1:

- **Definition:** Existence of comprehensive standardised metadata
- **Value range:**
 - 0: Non-standardised metadata
 - 1: Partially complying with standardised metadata model (e.g. HealthDCAT-AP)
 - 2: Fully complying with standardised metadata model (e.g. HealthDCAT-AP)
- **Recommended measurement approach:** Link/reference to the standardised metadata mode

Q1: Do you agree with this measure (definition and value range) to be used as part of the quality and fit-for-use labelling of a dataset in the context of HealthData@EU?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9
Strongly disagree Strongly agree

Q2 (non-mandatory): Would you suggest a different approach?

- Metadata scope - Measure #2:
 - **Definition:** Existence of an exhaustive data dictionary at variable level
 - **Value range:**
 - 0: No data dictionary
 - 1: Partial data dictionary: some variables described with basic information (i.e., names and brief definitions)
 - 2: Complete data dictionary: all variables described with detailed information (i.e., names, definitions, units, allowed values, etc.)
 - **Recommended measurement approach:** Link/reference to the standardised vocabularies in the meta-data model. Note that what the data dictionary contains may depend on the type of data; in the case of non-structured data the data dictionary may include features on the data source, its components and its relationship with other da

Q1: Do you agree with this measure (definition and value range) to be used as part of the quality and fit-for-use labelling of a dataset in the context of HealthData@EU?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9
Strongly disagree Strongly agree

Q2 (non-mandatory): Would you suggest a different approach?

VII. Accuracy

(Definition of the dimension: Accuracy refers to the degree to which observations correctly describe what it was designed to measure.)

- Accuracy - Measure #1:
 - **Definition:** Availability of an accuracy report
 - **Value range:**
 - 0: No such report
 - 1: Information on the efforts to ensure accuracy
 - 2: Statistical information on accuracy
 - **Recommended measurement approach:** The report should provide information on steps done to validate measurement accuracy of measured variables; in addition it should, at variable level, provide information on conformance to known (externally measured) distributions or to assumed value ranges of distributions

Q1: Do you agree with this measure (definition and value range) to be used as part of the quality and fit-for-use labelling of a dataset in the context of HealthData@EU?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9
Strongly disagree Strongly agree

Q2 (non-mandatory): Would you suggest a different approach?

VIII. Coherence

(Definition of the dimension: Coherence is defined as the dimension that expresses how different parts of the dataset are uniform in their representation and meaning over time, such as formats, semantics (stability of the data models), and methods.)

- Coherence - Measure #1:
 - **Definition:** Availability of a coherence report
 - **Value range:**
 - 0: No such report
 - 1: Partial information available
 - 2: Complete information on changes over time
 - **Recommended measurement approach:** At dataset level, the report should contain information on the changes observed in formats, semantics (stability of the data models), and methods

Q1: Do you agree with this measure (definition and value range) to be used as part of the quality and fit-for-use labelling of a dataset in the context of HealthData@EU?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9
Strongly disagree Strongly agree

Q2 (non-mandatory): Would you suggest a different approach?

IX. Completeness

(Definition of the dimension: Completeness refers to the degree to which all information that could be available is present in a particular dataset organized as tabular data.)

- Completeness - Measure #1:
 - **Definition:** Availability of a completeness report
 - **Value range:**
 - 0: No
 - 1: Some variables are analysed for completeness
 - 2: All variables are analysed for completeness
 - **Recommended measurement approach:** For each variable the dataset report should calculate the number of null values over the number of records. Explicit code values signifying that the information is not applicable are not considered null

Q1: Do you agree with this measure (definition and value range) to be used as part of the quality and fit-for-use labelling of a dataset in the context of HealthData@EU?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Strongly disagree Strongly agree

Q2 (non-mandatory): Would you suggest a different approach?

X. Consistency

(Definition of the dimension: Consistency refers to the degree to which data has attributes that are plausible and are uniform with other data and over time.)

- Consistency - Measure #1:
 - **Definition:** Availability of a consistency report
 - **Value range:**
 - 0: No
 - 1: Yes
 - **Recommended measurement approach:** For each variable the dataset report should contain consistency checks that refer to, amongst others: plausible range of numeric values; codings are plausible in relation to one another - "business logic" tests; use of valid codes (semantic).

Q1: Do you agree with this measure (definition and value range) to be used as part of the quality and fit-for-use labelling of a dataset in the context of HealthData@EU?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Strongly disagree Strongly agree

Q2 (non-mandatory): Would you suggest a different approach?

XI. Precision

(Definition of the dimension: Precision refers to the degree of approximation by which data can represent reality.)

- Precision - Measure #1:
 - **Definition:** Availability of a precision report
 - **Value range:**
0: No
1: Yes
 - **Recommended measurement approach:** For each variable, the dataset report should contain computational checks including amongst others: granularity in numeric variables; number of categories or ranges for grouped numeric variables; number of categories/codes used for ordinal or nominal variables

Q1: Do you agree with this measure (definition and value range) to be used as part of the quality and fit-for-use labelling of a dataset in the context of HealthData@EU?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9
Strongly disagree Strongly agree

Q2 (non-mandatory): Would you suggest a different approach?

XII. Validity

(Definition of the dimension: Validity refers to the degree to which representations of data in a dataset conform to the specification of a data model or data models.)

- Validity - Measure #1:
 - **Definition:** Availability of a conformance report for the data model
 - **Value range:**
0: No
1: Yes
 - **Recommended measurement approach:** For each variable, the dataset report should contain computational checks for variable level syntax conformance (.i.e., conformance with expected syntax as per the data model)

Q1: Do you agree with this measure (definition and value range) to be used as part of the quality and fit-for-use labelling of a dataset in the context of HealthData@EU?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9
Strongly disagree Strongly agree

Q2 (non-mandatory): Would you suggest a different approach?

Annex 5 - Online survey on weighting data dimensions, measures and thresholds

I. Weighting of data dimensions

- Please assess the relevance of the data quality & utility dimensions listed below in defining the Quantum label, **by allocating 100 tokens between the available dimensions.**
 - Priority dimensions should have more tokens. It is not necessary to allocate a minimum number of tokens for each dimension (just mention 0 in the text box).
 - All tokens must be used to validate the answer (the number of tokens remaining to be distributed is displayed under each question).
 - The sum must equal 100. Only integer values may be entered in these fields.
 - 1) Accessibility :
 - 2) Accuracy :
 - 3) Coherence :
 - 4) Completeness :
 - 5) Compliance :
 - 6) Consistency :
 - 7) Data provenance :
 - 8) Metadata scope :
 - 9) Population coverage :
 - 10) Population representativity :
 - 11) Precision :
 - 12) Validity :

II. Weighting of measures per dimension (for dimensions with two measures)

- Please assess the relevance of the measures listed below in defining the Quantum label, **by allocating 100 tokens between the available measures per dimension.**
 - Priority measures should have more tokens. It is not necessary to allocate a minimum number of tokens for each measure (just mention 0 in the text box).
 - All tokens must be used to validate the answer (the number of tokens remaining to be distributed is displayed under each question).
 - Only numbers may be entered in these fields. The sum must equal 100.
 - *Example: For a dimension with two measures, you may decide to allocate the tokens in the following ways: Measure A: 50; Measure B: 50 (both measures having the same level of relevance); Or Measure A: 75; Measure B: 25; Or Measure A: 100; Etc.*

Measures for accessibility

- 1) Availability of a data access & usage policy at the time of release of the dataset:
- 2) Average time from data access application to data release for a specific dataset:

Measures for data provenance

- 1) Is the source of the dataset documented?
- 2) Are the processes and operations on the data documented?

Measures for metadata scope

- 1) Existence of comprehensive standardised metadata
- 2) Existence of an exhaustive data dictionary at variable level

III. Evaluation of dataset quality levels

- Please evaluate the distribution of dataset quality levels, **indicating the scores (out of 100) required to obtain 1, 2, 3, 4 or 5 stars.**
 - Only integer values may be entered in these fields.
 - *Example: a score of 50 (%) is required for 1 star, 60 for 2 stars, 70 for 3 stars, 80 for 4 stars, 90 for 5 stars.*

Dataset quality levels - Ratings

- 1) 1 star dataset
- 2) 2 stars dataset
- 3) 3 stars dataset
- 4) 4 stars dataset
- 5) 5 stars dataset

- Dataset quality levels - **Comments** (non- mandatory question) :